

New Emerging Fast Charging Microscale Electrode Materials

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Abstract: Fast charging lithium (Li)-ion batteries are intensively pursued for next-generation energy storage devices, whose electrochemical performance is largely determined by their constituent electrode materials. In academic research, the strategy of nanosizing has been widely adopted to realize the high-rate capability by improving the kinetics of electrode materials. However, nanomaterials have several inherent limitations for practical applications, such as lower volumetric packing density and high synthetic cost. As an alternative to nanosizing, microscale electrode materials can not only effectively overcome the limitations of the nanosizing strategy but also satisfy the requirement of fast charging batteries. Therefore, this review summarizes the new emerging microscale electrode materials for fast charging from the commercialization perspective. First, the fundamental theory of electronic/ionic motion in both individual active particles and the whole electrode is proposed. Then, based on these theories, the corresponding optimization strategies are summarized towards fast charging microscale electrode materials. In addition, advanced functional design to tackle the mechanical degradation problems related to next generation high capacity alloy- and conversion-type electrode materials (Li, S, Si et.al.) for achieving fast charging and stable cycling batteries. Finally, general conclusions and the future perspective on the potential research directions of microscale electrode materials are proposed. We anticipate that this review will provide the basic guidelines for both fundamental research and practical applications of fast charging batteries.

1. Introduction

Fast charging technology of rechargeable batteries as an inevitable trend to meet requirement of accelerate worldwide market adoption of portable electronic devices, electric vehicles, and other electrochemical energy storage systems¹⁻⁸. Compared with gasoline vehicles, electric vehicles can only be truly competitive if the charging time is no longer than the refueling time. However, most of existing battery electric vehicles need 2 to 6 hours enable to achieve 250 miles cruise range, far from the ‘filling the tank’ experience and the target of 15 minutes recharge time (**Figure 1a**)^{9, 10}. Especially, the analysis of data throughout the *International Energy Agency* (IEA) shows that the Li-ion battery

demand has taken a huge leap forward in the last seven years (**Figure 1b**), primarily as a result of growth in electric vehicles sales. The market could be significantly larger as governments accelerate efforts to reach carbon neutral and reduce well-to-wheel greenhouse gas emissions. The increase in the number of electric cars resulted in an increased production of rechargeable batteries. However, the range anxiety caused by the limited driving range and charging time still check off the potential owners. Compared with other rechargeable batteries, lithium (Li)-ion batteries are intensively employed because of their high energy and power densities combined with lighter weight and smaller size (**Figure 1c**)¹¹. Currently, the energy density of commercial liquid Li-ion batteries for electric vehicles has reached $\approx 260 \text{ Wh Kg}^{-1}$ and 770 Wh L^{-1} with charging time on the order of tens of hours, which is closed to their limitations¹². Electric cars will only be truly competitive if the charging time is no longer than the time required to fill a gas tank. Thus, there is an ever-increasing demand for batteries with even higher energy and power densities.

As deposited in **Figure 1d**, there are several primary types of charging stations for electric vehicles, namely Level 1, Level 2, direct-current (DC) fast charger, Tesla super-charger, and extreme fast charger (XFC)¹³. It turns out that most chargers today are “Level 2”, which take 6 to 8 hours to score utterly charged batteries. DC fast chargers and Tesla super-charger with higher power and additional configurations induces by the increased voltage can shorten the time and extend the flexibility of electric vehicles. However, unlike overnight-slow charging, XFC within 15 minutes is the maximum acceptable to most drivers during traveling, similar to the refueling experience of conventional vehicles. No doubt that the charging rate increases with the charging power. It can be seen from **Figure 1e** that the 300-kW level charging power is essential for the pack size of 90 kWh charged in 15 minutes. Hence, it can be concluded that Li-ion batteries are the major technical barrier to the successful realization of XFC, whose electrochemical performance is determined largely by constituent electrode materials.

Figure 1. (a) The comparison of the ‘filling the tank’ experience, the current charging time and the target of recharge in 15 minutes for 250 miles cruise range. (b) The Li-ion battery demand by region during 2016-2022 across regions and the year-over-year growth over the past few years. The analysis date is from the *International Energy Agency*. (c) Present status and development trend of the volume energy density and the gravimetric energy density in rechargeable batteries. (d) Comparison of currently available charging methods. (e) Time charging and corresponding charging rate for different battery packs as a function of charger power. c) Reproduced with permission ¹¹. Copyright 2020, Wiley-VCH. d, e) Reproduced with permission. ¹³ Copyright 2019, Nature Publishing Group.

The electrochemical performance of fast charging batteries is largely defined by electrons and ions kinetics within electrode materials. Conventional microscale bulk electrodes normally suffer from slow solid-state ionic diffusion, high electronic resistance and mechanical degradation at both particle and electrode levels, all of which significantly limit their fast charging performance. The emergence and development of nanotechnology offers a promising approach to designing high-performance electrode materials - nanosizing electrode materials.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ In comparison to the conventional bulk electrode materials, nanometer-sized active materials have shorter ion diffusion and electronic transfer distances, and much more electrochemical reaction sites owing to the increased specific surface area.^{18, 19} However, the practical application of nanomaterials in commercial batteries has been limited, only LiFePO₄^{20, 21} and Si²²⁻²⁴ electrodes have benefited from this approach. Indeed, although the size reduction of active materials to the nanometer level enables rapid electrochemical process and high-rate performance²⁵, the negative effects must not be overlooked. The issues and limitations associated with nanomaterials in Li-ion batteries are summarized in **Figure 2**.

From configuration perspective, compared with the micrometer-sized materials, the decreased particle size of nanosized active materials results in a lower tap density due to the increased interparticle space (**Figure 2a**)¹⁴. The low tap density of nanomaterials results in a much lower volumetric packing density and a thicker electrode needed to achieve a considerable capacity level compared with the micron-sized electrode materials^{26, 27}. Moreover, the thick electrodes have poor charge transfer kinetics, especially for nanometer-sized active materials within conventional electrode configurations - the sluggish charge kinetics within the thick electrodes require more time for ions to reach the active sites and lead to the limited rate performance^{28, 29}. The enhanced specific surface area of nanosized active materials consumes more electrolyte and alkali metal, leading to low initial coulombic efficiency and highly irreversible capacity loss.³⁰ As deposited in **Figure 2b**, the specific solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) area of ~80 nm nanoparticles ($\sim 90 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) is approximately 60 times higher than the 10 μm particles ($1.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$)³¹. Apart from side reactions caused by the formation

of electrode/electrolyte interface, chemical evolution and irreversible structural transformations at the surface of active materials induced by the electrode-electrolyte interactions during electrochemical cycling can also contribute to the performance degradation, including capacity fading and voltage instability^{32, 33}.

From synthesis perspective, reducing electrode materials to the nanoscale through hydrothermal reactions and the sol-gel method (**Figure 2c**) increase the cost of the battery components³⁴⁻³⁸. Moreover, the synthesis methods are usually complex and often require strict pressure temperature control. Thus, more considerations should be taken to lower the cost and achieve economic viability.

From operation perspective, the nanoscale materials often evolve drastically during operation. For instance, **Figure 2d** shows the loose atomic layers and the surface reconstruction on the charged cathode particles^{39, 40}. The problems related to surface structure evolution can be enlarged by the inherently high surface area of materials. Similarly, the chemical nonuniformity of nanosized active materials brings new challenges in controlling the practicable chemistry and electrochemical performance. The high surface energy of nanomaterials can also lead to the inhomogeneity of anions during the synthesis process (e.g., chemical nonuniformity of FeOF nanomaterials shown in **Figure 2e**). The local structural and chemical disordering of the FeOF nanomaterials may be induced by the thermodynamic instability of oxygen-substituted phase. The inhomogeneous distribution of elements unquestionably leads to undesirable electrochemical processes during the cycling⁴¹. Similarly, Li/Fe ions disordering on the surface of LiFePO₄ was identified as an energy reconfiguration, inducing by the crystallographic orientation on the subsurface.⁴² The defect formation often brings more challenges to the controllable synthesis of materials with target properties. Hence, it is not only necessary to consider the typical Li diffusion channels in bulk crystals, but also to understand the defect physics/chemistry and their role in electrode properties.

From the thermodynamic perspective, nanoparticles within the electrode material tend to minimize their Gibbs free energy by agglomeration. This process not only makes it difficult to retain

the original morphology of electrode material but also leads to high interparticle resistance. The driving force of nanomaterials aggregation is related to the destabilized free energy resulting from the high surface-area-to-volume ratio. Detailed parameters that affect the driving force of aggregation have been studied by the theory of Derjaguin – Landau – Verwey – Overbeek (DLVO)^{43, 44}. Due to the instability surface of materials, the competition of attractive and repulsive forces between two nanoparticles has always existed. All the same, particles with nano-size (e.g., <100 nm) usually amplify these properties. As is known, rapid electron/ion transport at the electrode level is more important than at the independent particle level^{45, 46}. If high-flux transmission at the electrode level is difficult to achieve, then this is very detrimental to the high-mass-loading of a practical battery. What's more, the short-range ordering and recombination reactions of sub-Angström-level clusters may lead to the irreversibility of reconversion reaction, further resulting in poor cyclability and drastically reduction in electrochemical activity (**Figure 2f**). Analogously, the nano-size effect may substantially affect the electrochemical redox potential values, which are induced by enhanced Gibbs free energy formation of the excessive surface.⁴⁷ Especially, tremendous surface energy changes can lead to a series of non-ideal results, such as undesired catalysis, side reactions, and lower stability. Therefore, it is important to point out that nano-level materials does not always represent better⁴⁸. Considering the various issues of nanomaterials used in working batteries, rationally designed microscale electrode materials with unique structures have become one of the enticing and promising choices for fast charging batteries^{13, 49}. The new emerging electrode materials should combine the advantages of both nanoscale and microscale electrode materials for scalable applications of fast charging Li batteries (**Figure 2g**). Besides, the criterions of micro-scale electrode materials for fast charging should overcome the limitations of nanomaterials in battery system, such as surface reactivity, low tap density, physical and chemical nonuniformity, and high synthetic cost.

Figure 2. The inherent limitations of nanomaterials in the field of electrochemical batteries. (a) Low volumetric energy density. Compared with the micron-sized particles, the tap density of nanomaterials is much lower. (b) Surface degradation and low initial coulombic efficiency induced by the large surface area of cathode–electrolyte interface (CEI) or solid electrolyte interphase (SEI). (c) The high processing cost and difficult to fabricate on large scales of nanoscale electrode materials. (d) Irreversible structure evolution of NCM and LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ cathode materials during cycling. The higher surface area of nanomaterials, the more irreversible structure changes. (e) Chemical

nonuniformity of FeOF nanomaterials: STEM-EELS spectrum-images for the elemental distribution of O (green) from many locations (scale bar: 5 nm). The highly anisotropic characteristics of LiFePO₄ at each face. (f) The high surface destabilized free energy of nanomaterials is the main reason for aggregation. The aggregation of nanomaterials leads to the degradation of battery performance. (g) The summary radar plot of salient features of nanoscale and microscale electrode materials. a, b) Reproduced with permission.¹⁴ Copyright 2016, Nature Publishing Group. c) Reproduced with permission.³⁴ Copyright 2014, Elsevier. d) Reproduced with permission.³⁹ Copyright 2014, Nature Publishing Group. Reproduced with permission.⁴⁰ Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society. e) Reproduced with permission.⁴¹ Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society. Reproduced with permission.⁴² Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society. f) Reproduced with permission.⁴³ Copyright 2010, John Wiley and Sons. Reproduced with permission.⁵⁰ Copyright 2011, American Chemical Society.

In this review, we focus on the new emerging fast charging microscale electrode materials. Since high-power anode and cathode materials share the same requirement: ion diffusion, charge transfer, and structural stability. Thus, instead of considering individual components, we organize this review around the design solutions addressing the challenges encountered with nanomaterial-based electrodes and conventional microscale bulk electrodes. First, it describes the rate-limiting mechanisms and fundamental guidance for fast charging electrode materials in a working battery, including intrinsic electrode materials engineering and electrode materials design. Further, the summary of optimization strategies and the mechanisms for the fast charging microscale electrode materials are presented, such as micronization electrode materials with nanoscale contributions, microscale fast charging electrode materials in engineering design and self-healing functional microscale electrode materials with certain potential to enhance the reliability and service life of fast-charging, which in turn give more directions to design and explore new high power density electrode materials without compromising energy density. Finally, we discuss the

challenges and possible directions in the future development of microscale electrode materials, which facilitates both fundamental research and practical applications of fast charging rechargeable batteries.

2. Fundamental Mechanism of Transport Kinetics for Fast Charging Microscale Electrode Materials

Figure 3. (a) Classic impedance with frequency and associated individual cell components. (b-e) Schematic illustration of the ion and electron transport system and multi-scale considerations inside the composite electrode in battery configuration.⁵¹⁻⁵³ (f) Classification of the main factors affecting electron and ion transport and corresponding consideration for designing the electrode materials for fast charging. b) Reproduced with permission.⁵³ Copyright 2020, Wiley-VCH. c) Reproduced with permission.⁵² Copyright 2020, Nature Publishing Group. e) Reproduced with permission.⁵¹ Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society.

Understanding the working mechanism of batteries is vital for redesigning the traditional microscale electrode materials and overcoming the limitations of nanomaterials. The basic principle of electrochemical batteries involves the storage and transport of ionic/electron throughout the system under the structural and dynamic factors accompanying phase transition. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a non-destructive method for analyzing the dynamic process occurring inside a battery.⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶ The typical Nyquist plot and the equivalent circuit of the rechargeable ion batteries is shown in **Figure 3a**. Models are used in the form of equivalent electrical circuits with different frequency ranges, including resistance (R), capacitance (C), elements, and constant phase element (CPE), to represent departures from ideality to assign these to different physical processes and components within the battery⁵⁶. Furthermore, a comprehensive exploration of multi-scale ion/electron transport is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of how to improve fast charging performance⁵⁷. Charging time depends on the charge storage and conversion processes, as deposited in **Figure 3b-e**, including b) electron conduction and ion transport simultaneously moving towards the active materials, c) ion/electron transport inside the active materials, d) charge transfer and ion de-solvation at the interface, e) electron transfer along the network formed by the electrically conductive additive and ion transport in bulk electrolyte along the concentration gradient^{46, 51-53, 58, 59}. Already, each dynamic process can cover disparate spatial and temporal scales, as well as related to upper and lower bounds of batteries (from atom to pack).

Specifically, the main difficulty in fast charging batteries is kinetic issues due to sluggish mass transport or charge transfer.⁶⁰ Many primary factors affect the charge and ion transport inside the composite electrodes. Although structural and dynamics factors are very complicated and tough to identify, the intrinsic electrode materials (active materials) and electrode-level materials engineering (charge/ion transport network and pore engineering) are the fundamental considerations to boost the electrode materials for fast charging (**Figure 3f**). In addition, the complicated interfaces factors among various materials and the environmental factors (e.g. temperature, applied pressure) can

notably affect the dynamics factors, which is not a focus discussed in this review. Therefore, in the topic review, the primary goal of the fundamental mechanism of transport kinetics for fast charging microscale electrode materials summarized here is focus on the intrinsic electrode materials and electrode-level materials engineering considerations for promoting fast charging.

2.1 Intrinsic Ionic and Electronic Conductivity of Active Materials

It is typically believed that the fundamental limitations to the rate in the electrochemical battery system are the ionic and electron kinetics within active particles.⁶¹ Hence, the rate performance of battery materials can be enhanced when the limitations of ionic and electron transport are overcome.

2.1.1 The Requirement of Ionic Conduction for Fast Charging

Understanding the ionic transport mechanism is an essential step to optimize the electrode materials for efficient battery performance, including rate performance, cycling stability, and practical capacity.⁶²⁻⁶⁷ Diffusion is governed by random hops of atoms or ions between different sites of the crystal. This process in general is described by the second Fick's law⁶⁸, which has been used to determine the Li^+ diffusion coefficients D_{Li^+} .

$$D_{\text{Li}^+} = \frac{4}{\pi} \left(\frac{m_B V_M}{M_B A} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta E s}{\tau (dE\tau / d\sqrt{\tau})} \right)^2 \left(\tau \square \frac{L^2}{D_{\text{Li}^+}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where V_M is the molar volume of the active material; M_B is the molecular weight of the materials; m_B is the mass of the active materials in an electrode; L is the Li diffusion distance (thickness of the electrode); A is the electrode area; and τ is the duration time. When the variation of cell voltage during titration was found to show a straight line behavior on plotting against $\tau^{1/2}$ Eq. (2) can be further simplified as⁶⁹:

$$D_{\text{Li}^+} = \frac{4}{\pi\tau} \left(\frac{m_B V_M}{M_B A} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta E s}{\Delta E \tau} \right)^2 \left(\tau \square \frac{L^2}{D_{\text{Li}^+}} \right) \quad (2)$$

According to the solution of one-dimensional Fick's second law for an electrode film with a finite thickness (l) and constant Li-ion diffusivity (D), the normalized Li-ion concentration (C_{Li^+}) can be described as a function of distance (x) and time (t) by

$$C_{Li^+} = 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{2n+1} \exp\left\{-\frac{D(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{4l^2}\right\} \cos \frac{(2n+1)\pi x}{2l} \quad (3)$$

This simplified diffusion model⁷⁰ indicates that concentration polarization is more serious at high rates and it only can be minimized by increasing the characteristic diffusion length (Dt) and decreasing material thickness (l). In the case of fast charging batteries, this implies that the diffusivity of Li-ions should be maximized to reach better performance.

It should be noted that the intrinsic host structures, grain boundaries, and micro/nanostructure of electrode materials also play an important role in the diffusion process, which will be elaborated in detail in later sections. The above expression concerning ionic transport mechanisms provided key parameters and strategies for higher ion diffusivity and improvement of rate performance of electrode materials: more active sites (surface effects) and vacant sites, creating well-connected channels, designing and regulating the pristine lattice and electronic structure of electrode materials.

2.1.2 The Requirement of Electronic Conduction for Fast Charging

The electrode materials must be ionic/electron mixed conductors, as their performance is largely defined by simultaneous insertion/deinsertion of ions and electrons during the charge and discharge process.⁷¹ Thus, Kim et al. have indicated that the low electronic conductivity is undesirable to battery performance under high rates, especially for the highly insulating cathode and anode materials.⁷² It means only partial ions are involved in the redox reaction, and unattractive low capacity under high rates when the electronic conductivity is extremely low ($< \sim 10^{-5}$ S/cm).^{9, 73} The high resistance means electrons to flow with high hindrance and increases the heat generation., and excessive heat can damage a battery. Besides, the low electronic conductivity electrode materials in the batteries have

bigger electronic resistances and ohmic losses. The relationship between resistance and resistivity is given by:

$$R(\Omega) = \rho(\Omega \text{ cm}) \frac{l(\text{cm})}{A(\text{cm}^2)} \quad (4)$$

It clearly shows that the resistance (R) can be decreased by using low resistivity (ρ) over a large area (A) and a thinner electrode thickness. However, current thin-film electrodes have very few active materials relative to binders, conductive agents, and other passive components. The low active materials loading induces devices with low energy density and cannot satisfy the requirements of practical applications⁷.

In general, mean-field-based theory has been widely used to describe the electronic properties of materials. However, one should note that band gap energies and even the metal/insulator nature of materials are largely defined by the level of the theory used in their description⁷⁴. Thus, while the electronic structures of a wide family of materials are available in open-access databases⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷, it is often impossible to conclude which of the two materials are more conductive. Indeed, the description of free carrier mobility requires knowledge of not only the electronic structure but also an accurate prediction of free carrier concentration defined by the charge neutrality rule of defect compensation⁷⁸. The latter is mainly defined by synthesis and operational conditions.

2.1.3 Optimizing the Conductivity of Particle Level Electrode Materials

In addition to the above mechanism and key factors, tuning the composition of active materials has been investigated to improve both ionic and electron transport. Generally, surface coating and atomic doping are the most widely applied modification methods to engineer the composition of active materials.

For surface coating, the approach can reduce the surface resistance and the contact between electrode material and electrolyte can be minimized to reduce the occurrence of side reactions. The formation of a stable electrode/electrolyte interface is critical to ensure efficient charge transfer and ion diffusion. Besides, surface coating modification is an effective method to solve interface issues.

Among various coating materials, carbon coating has been demonstrated to be an effective strategy to boost electrical conductivity and chemical corrosion resistance, especially in alkali batteries with organic electrolytes. It is worth noting that the degree of carbon contact and graphitization, coating amount, and thickness have a significant effect on the performance. The excessive coating will restrict the transfer of ions and lead to an increase in polarization. Graphitic carbon and intimate contact are required for higher conductivity and thus better rate performance. Besides, other carbon-free coating conductive films, such as polypyrrole (PPy) and polyaniline (PANI) conductive polymer, Ag, NiP, Al₂O₃/TiO₂, and so on⁷⁹⁻⁸¹, coated on the surface of electrode materials can also increase the electrochemical performance.⁸² For example, the metallic NiP coating on the LiFePO₄ cathode not only can increase conductivity but also can promote morphological and structural stability upon cycling.⁸³ Except for the aforementioned single conductive coating materials, various fast ionic conductors and electron-ion mixed conductors, such as Nd_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO₃,⁸⁴ LiNbO₃,⁸⁵ LiAlF₄,⁸⁶ have been applied as surface coating materials to facilitate the migration of ion and electron.

At the same time, it is noteworthy that surface coating of electrode materials offers superiority in terms of enhance charge transfer and electrochemical performance, but it also introduces potential challenges related to manufacturing complexity and degradation. On one hand, surface coating comes with complexity to the manufacturing process, potentially increasing production costs and energy consumption. Meanwhile, maintaining a uniform and precise thickness of the coating can be challenging, as variations can affect the overall performance. On the other hand, the surface coating carries a potential risk of degradation, cracking or delamination, which could lead to a decrease in performance or device failure. Therefore, the choice to employ surface coatings to enhance fast charging should be made based on the specific requirements of the application and the trade-offs involved.

For atomic doping, unlike surface coating, the substitution of a few ions in the lattice by doping can improve the intrinsic conductivity of electrode materials, and not just the surface effects. In detail,

surface coating modification has a significant effect on promoting the migration of electrons/ions on the electrode/electrolyte surface. However, the bulk structure of electrode materials is the key to electrochemical performance. In general, doping has been proven effective in enhancing capacity delivery, cycle life, and rate performance of electrode materials.^{82,87,88} The performance improvement comes from the changes in the electronic structure of frontier states and crystal structural stability,⁸⁹ which is crucial for achieving fast charging. In detail, n-type (p-type) doping increases the electron (hole) free carrier concentration resulting in increased carrier conductivity. By introducing other heteroatoms, heteroatom-doped electrode materials have enlarged lattice constants, increased active sites, as well as improved morphology and crystal structural stability during Li deintercalation/intercalation, enabling stable cycling and high rate capacity.⁹⁰⁻⁹³ Significant correlation between the electrochemical performance and doping of electrode materials has been confirmed.^{91, 94, 95} Graphite is the first commercial anode for Li-ion batteries. However, it has encountered some troubles catering to the ever-increasing demand for high-performance anodes⁹⁶, such as limited theoretical energy density (372 mA h g⁻¹) and poor rate performance. Doping of non-carbon elements, such as N, S, P, can stimulate high chemical reactivity and electronic conductivity, and thus mitigate the above issues. Huang et al. prepared the high-level nitrogen doping porous carbon that significantly enhanced the reversible capacity and rate capability. The capacity can be reached 226 mA h g⁻¹ at an extremely high current density of 20 A/g (~ 40 s to full charge).⁹¹

2.2 Electrode-level Considerations for Promoting Fast Charging

The real performance of a fast charging battery is restricted by kinetic factors, not only at the level of the active material but also at the level of electrodes. Apart from using an electrode material with high electron/ion transfer, building a robust electron/ion transport network is essential to enhance electrochemical performance and energy density. The importance of the microstructure of electrode materials at the electrode level has been widely demonstrated.^{97, 98} Generally, electrode-level

structural engineering, including both electron and ion transport networks, is an effective approach to achieving high-power-density batteries.

2.2.1 Electron Transport Networks Engineering

In pursuit of the ultimate design in microscale fast charging electrode materials, the interparticle electron transport within the electrode is an important factor. The electrochemical hysteresis of microscale electrode materials is always caused by the interparticle resistance, hindering the advantage of fast kinetics of single active materials.⁹⁹ In addition, the morphology complexity of active materials with limited connecting impede electron transfer along the whole electrode.^{100, 101} Thus, the work efficiency of electron transport networks at the electrode level is critical to boosting the electrochemical performance of active materials.

Traditionally, random packing of the conductive agent in the conventional composite electrode constructs the electron transport networks. According to the percolation theory, it contains three kinds of conductive agents, including 0D (carbon black), 1D (carbon nanotubes), and 2D (graphene-based) materials. However, the random packing electron transport networks demonstrated less structure controllability.^{102, 103} Recently, electrode scaffolds including 1D, 2D, and 3D with continuous conductive networks have been widely developed. Compared with the conventional random packing conductive agents, the well-controlled continuous structures provide fast and continuous conductive networks. In particular, 1D and 2D electrode scaffolds enable highly efficient charge delivery to active sites and induce a sufficient electrochemical reaction. However, the energy density is limited by finite active materials per unit/volume. Besides, for the architectures of both 1D and 2D, it is a great challenge to withstand the large volume/strain changes during cycling.¹⁰⁴ In contrast, 3D continuous networks can improve the structural stability of the entire electrode, and ensure efficient charge delivery. More importantly, thanks to the interconnected porous structure for ion transport and continuous conductive networks for electron transport, the 3D-based electrodes have shown significant advantages for the utilization of high mass loading electrodes ($\geq 10 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$) under the

requirement of commercial cells. 3D-based scaffolds will be necessary for the realization of high-power density and high-energy-density storage because of their high surface area, excellent conductivity and continuous electron transport networks to ensure sufficient electron transport.^{105, 106} Such a 3D electrode can overcome the limitations of nanomaterials and translate the extraordinary performance achieved by nanoscale materials into macroscopic electrodes with high mass loading. Typical examples with detailed descriptions will be introduced in later sections (Section 4.1).

2.2.2 Ions Transport Networks Engineering

In general, the sluggish ions transport kinetics at high rates is the major contributor to capacity losses, especially for the high mass loading electrode. The design of tortuosity and pore structures, associated with improved transport, kinetic, and thermodynamic properties, are the two strategies to enhance ion diffusion capability on the electrode level.¹⁰⁷ Therefore, the quantitative measurement of structural parameters will assist in-depth understanding of the relationship between the structure and performance of electrode materials.¹⁰⁸ 3D imaging techniques and modern data science techniques have been developed to accurately quantify spatially dependent parameters. Data analysis can show what the dominant rate-limiting process is in a given situation, further promoting the rational design of electrode materials. Here, we will not elaborate on the above techniques for quantifying the electrode structures, and we suggest that readers refer to these related articles.^{26, 98, 109}

As is known, tortuosity (τ) is the square ratio of the length of the streamline through a porous structure (Δl) to the distance between its ends (Δx), as present in Equation (5):

$$\tau = \left(\frac{\Delta l}{\Delta x} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

However, for the porous electrodes, tortuosity is not always presented precisely. It is combined with intrinsic ion diffusivity (D_0) and effective relative ion diffusivity (D_{eff}), defined generally as^{108, 110, 111}:

$$\tau = \varepsilon \left(\frac{D_0}{D_{eff}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where ε is the porosity of the electrode. The tortuosity of the electrode hinges on the porous structure (i.e., pore size, direction, and shape distribution). Employing the relationship between porosity and tortuosity is the most fundamental way to derive the tortuosity of the electrode. Bruggeman equation is the most widespread relation in the field, defined as Equation (7)^{112, 113}:

$$\tau^2 = \lambda \varepsilon^{1-\alpha} \quad (7)$$

where α is the Bruggeman exponent and considered as 1.5. It should be noticed that the predictions given by the Bruggeman correlation are not always consistent with experimental results¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶. The additional scaling factor λ is used for correlating the model with the experiments. According to the relationship, it can be concluded that tortuosity increases non-linearly with porosity. The above mechanisms propose some prospective architectural designs according to the relationship between porosity and tortuosity.¹¹⁷ The ideal porous electrode structure requires a tortuosity of 1, which is much lower than the tortuosity (3~5) in conventional electrodes. Thus, rational design of low tortuosity electrodes can boost fast charging by building rapid ion transport networks and shortening ion diffusion paths.

In the above sections, we have introduced the electrode-level considerations based on either electron or ions transport networks engineering. Actually, both electron and ions transport networks are usually entangled and interconnected. That is, the basic mechanism of electrochemical batteries is transport of both ionic and electron throughout the battery system. The intertwining of electron and ion transport networks is the reason a functional battery operates as a unified system, making it challenging to separate them without adversely affecting the battery's overall performance. Therefore, electrode-level considerations and engineering must consider the interconnected nature of these transport mechanisms for promoting fast charging.

3. Emerging Micronization Electrode Materials with Nanoscale Contributions

When rechargeable Li-ion batteries became commercially available in the 1990s, the traditional electrode materials were primarily on a milli- or microscale in size. However, the sluggish diffusion dynamics of such materials fail to meet the increasing energy or power density demand for electric vehicles. Since electrode materials hold the key to the new generation of energy storage and conversion devices, substantial efforts have been dedicated to develop electrode materials with higher energy and power density. During the past decade, the most common approach to achieving fast charging electrodes is to reduce the active material size to the nanometer level, which minimizes ion and electron diffusion paths.^{118, 119} Nevertheless, the nanoparticles with increased interface with electrolyte induce deleterious side reactions and poor volumetric energy density, limiting their industrial application.¹²⁰ In this section, the strategies to obtain the microscale fast charging electrode materials with nanoscale attributes will be explained in detail through certain examples, facilitating the design of electrode materials with high power density.

3.1 Intrinsic Micron-sized Electrode Materials with Appropriate Crystal Structures

Understanding the relationship between lattice structure and electrochemical performance has always been a constant driving force for improving and discovering electrode materials. Fundamentally, the energy density of a battery equals the product of the specific capacity and the working voltage. The working voltage of a battery is determined by the electrochemical potential difference between the cathode (μ_C) and anode (μ_A).¹²¹⁻¹²⁵ Thermodynamically, the maximum allowed voltage window of electrolytes is limited by the energy gap (E_g) between the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMO) and the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO) (**Figure 4a**). The choices of electrode materials must follow the principle, μ_A located below the LUMO and μ_C above the HOMO. The above properties of electrode materials are heavily determined by their chemical composition, crystal, and electronic structure, which can be described by Gibbs free energy and Fermi energy level. The calculated electrochemical potential of common electrode materials is shown in **Figure 4b**.¹²⁶ Ionic storage and transport reversibly in lattice sites or spaces of

electrodes provide the principle for power batteries. Therefore, a well-designed lattice structure and ion-electronic channels are essential for high-performance electrode materials.¹²⁷⁻¹²⁹

Figure 4. (a) The voltage window of battery E_g , where μ_A located below the LUMO and μ_C above the HOMO. (b) The calculated electrochemical potential of common LIB electrode materials. (c, d, e) Illustration of the crystal structures of the traditional Li transition metal oxides (LTMOs) materials and the open framework structure which allows for facile ionic transport. a) Reproduced with permission.¹²³ Copyright 2016, Elsevier. b) Reproduced with permission.¹²⁶ Copyright 2016, Elsevier.

For fast charging applications, the energy density decreases with the increasing rate, which is attributed to the disequilibrium of ionic and electrons transfer within the electrode and interface. Generally, ionic transfer is much slower to match the charge balance. Therefore, the appropriate ion migration routes or kinetic barriers are required for electrodes in high-rate batteries. To date, intensive efforts have been devoted to developing various electrode materials with appropriate host structures or efficient ion and electron transport channels. According to the type of Li-ion transport channels,

the traditional Li transition metal oxides (LTMOs) can be classified into the following types, namely 1D olivine LiMPO_4 (M= Fe, Mn, Co, Ni, etc.), 2D layered LiMO_2 (M = Ni, Co, Mn, Al), 3D spinel $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and LiMn_2O_4 (**Figure 4c-e**).¹³⁰⁻¹³² Excitedly, all of the above cathode materials show the prospects of high-rate batteries.

Understanding of the fundamental mechanism acquired on current electrodes provides insights into designing new fast charging electrode materials. It is generally believed that the absence of phase transition, involving structural rearrangements and large volume changes, is the key for achieving high rates, such as LiCoO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 , $\text{Li}(\text{Ni}; \text{Co}; \text{Al})\text{O}_2$, and $\text{Li}(\text{Ni}; \text{Co}; \text{Mn})\text{O}_2$. In addition to ionic diffusion, there are few kinetic barriers for the continuous accommodation of Li through solid solution transformation (**Figure 5a**).¹³³⁻¹³⁸ When a phase transformation is induced during accommodating Li atoms within the electrode materials, the excellent rate performance can be obtained via a non-equilibrium solid solution phase transformation process. In this case, Li ions percolate through LiFePO_4 or its delithiated form, FePO_4 , toward or away from the phase boundary between these two line phases.^{139, 140} However, the remarkable rate capability of LiFePO_4 derives from the single-phase transformation path without nucleation and growth of a second phase. The existence of a non-equilibrium solid solution phase (Li_xFePO_4 , $0 < x < 1$) during the phase transformation path makes it unnecessary to overcome extra kinetic barriers (**Figure 5b**)¹³⁹. It is worth noting that the main obstacle to practical applications of micro-sized LiFePO_4 is its poor electronic conductivity ($< 10^{-9} \text{ S/cm}^2$)¹⁴¹,

142.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of phase transition mechanism (a) Two-phase reaction and solid-solution reaction. Solid solution transformation with few kinetic barriers is suitable for fast charging batteries. (b) Non-equilibrium solid solution phase transformation process without nucleation and growth of a second phase. (c) Illustration of electrochemical functional battery working in TEM. The ion migration pathways (d) and the corresponding energy barriers (e) in the intermediates. The much lower ion migration barriers of the face-sharing motifs induce the high-rate capability. a) Reproduced with permission.¹³⁴ Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society. b) Reproduced with permission.¹³⁹ Copyright 2014, American Association for the Advancement of Science. c-e) Reproduced with permission.¹⁴³ Copyright 2020, American Association for the Advancement of Science.

Another exception within the type of phase transformation is the spinel $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ anode, which transforms into the rock-salt phase $\text{Li}_7\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ with negligible volume change.¹⁴⁴⁻¹⁴⁸ As is known, the commercialized graphite anode suffers from sluggish lithium intercalation kinetics and a lower

lithium intercalation potential (0.08V vs Li/Li⁺). Under high current densities, substantial polarization can drive the lithium intercalation potential dangerously close to the threshold for the deposition of metallic lithium ($\approx 0.00\text{V vs Li/Li}^+$), increasing the risk of Li dendrite formation and serious severe accidents¹⁴⁹. Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ anode undergo lithium intercalation and deintercalation reactions at a high redox potential of approximately 1.55 V, effectively preventing the formation of SEI films and lithium dendrites, thus enhancing safety. Specifically, the recent study shows that the fast ion transport routes in the metastable intermediates Li_{4+x}Ti₅O₁₂ are enabled in the intermediate configurations involving face-sharing Li polyhedral.¹⁴³ The researchers developed an electrochemical functional battery that works in a transmission electron microscope (TEM), allowing the manipulative characterization of electrode materials (**Figure 5c**). As demonstrated in **Figure 5d-e**, compared with Li_{4+ δ} Ti₅O₁₂ and Li_{7- δ} Ti₅O₁₂, the high-rate capability is induced by the much lower ion migration barriers of the face sharing motifs and the formation energy of their intermediates (Li_{5+ δ} Ti₅O₁₂). However, the disadvantages of the present Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ cannot be neglected. The low specific capacity (175 mAh g⁻¹) and higher working potential ($\approx 1.55\text{ V vs Li}^+/\text{Li}$) will cause a much lower battery energy density¹⁵⁰. Nonetheless, an in-depth understanding of the above mechanisms will help to design and search for new microscale fast charging electrode materials with advanced crystal structures.

During the process of intensive seeking new fast charging electrode materials, Bruce and co-workers demonstrated the fluorinated disordered and Li excessed LiMn₂O₄ spinel structure with both dense and fast energy storage with reversible Mn and O redox, namely two Li-rich cathodes: Li_{1.68}Mn_{1.6}O_{3.7}F_{0.3} (LMOF03) and Li_{1.68}Mn_{1.6}O_{3.4}F_{0.6} (LMOF06) (**Figure 6a**).¹⁵¹ Compared with the LiMn₂O₄, the excess Li can increase the O-TM channels concentration, enabling higher capacity and higher Li mobility, while the tunability in F substitution reduces valences of Mn and enhances the cyclability simultaneously. Interestingly, the active O redox process was observed at high rates, challenging conventional view (**Figure 6b**). Following the above design strategy, the ultra-high

energy density $> 1,100 \text{ W h kg}^{-1}$ ($> 360 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$) and a discharge rate up to 20 A g^{-1} were obtained under conditions of high carbon and low mass loading. Although the primary active particle size is 100-200 nm for LMOF03 and 100-300 nm for LMOF06 (similar to commercial LiFePO_4), investigation new methods for synthesizing micron-sized of these materials merit further attention.

Figure 6. (a) Schematic illustration of modifications and local environments to the spinel LiMn_2O_4 : cation order with substantial Li excess and F substitution, which can increase the available Li and O-TM channels concentration and induces higher capacity and higher Li mobility. (b) The electrochemistry quantification of Mn redox reactions of LMOF03 during the 1st cycle indicates the active O redox process. (c) Left: Crystal structure and particle morphology of the block structure $\text{Nb}_{16}\text{W}_5\text{O}_{55}$, which indicate the micron-sized particle with 3D open lattice structures. Right: anisotropic change in lattice parameters host-lattice response during Li intercalation $\text{Nb}_{16}\text{W}_5\text{O}_{55}$, which can buffer the volume change. (d) The comparison of the volumetric capacity of $\text{Nb}_{16}\text{W}_5\text{O}_{55}$ and $\text{Nb}_{18}\text{W}_{16}\text{O}_{93}$ to the state-of-art nanoscale anode materials. a) Reproduced with permission.¹⁵¹

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Recently, Grey et al. demonstrated $\text{Nb}_{16}\text{W}_5\text{O}_{55}$ and $\text{Nb}_{18}\text{W}_{16}\text{O}_{93}$ as alternatives for the safe and fast charging $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ anode.¹⁵² The two complex niobium tungsten oxides have suitable 3D crystal structures and show extremely high-rate performance, even though the primary particle size is on the micrometer (3–10 μm) scale (**Figure 6c**). The anisotropic host-lattice response to Li intercalation and multielectron redox capabilities (Nb^{5+} and W^{6+}) leads to small volume expansion and high theoretical capacities (300~400 mA h g^{-1}). The diffusion coefficients of the two complex micrometre-sized niobium tungsten oxides with open structural motifs reach the order of 10^{-12} - 10^{-13} $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, which are several orders of magnitude higher than the $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ anode and meet the requirement of achieving full lithiation of 10 μm particles on a 60 C timescale. As shown in **Figure 6d**, the volumetric capacity for two complex niobium tungsten oxides is much larger than the state-of-art nanoscale anode materials and have implications for small volume energy storage devices. Inspired by the above work, Liu and co-workers synthesized the micro-sized $\text{Nb}_{14}\text{W}_3\text{O}_{44}$ (NWO) by the facile solution combustion method.⁵¹ Same as the above two complex niobium tungsten oxides, the NWO adopts I-4 tetragonal symmetry and corner-shared NbO_6 and WO_6 octahedra, building the facile Li-ion diffusion pathways within the open tunnel network. As a result, the micrometer-sized NWO active particles delivered an excellent rate capability of 130 mA h g^{-1} at 10 C. The strategy of designing an appropriate host lattice without the assistance of nanosizing shows great application potential in high dense and power batteries.^{52, 153} However, the research on complex niobium tungsten oxides high rate lithium-ion negative electrode materials is still in its early stages, and some key issues still need to be further explored in order to achieve large-scale applications. For example, the higher redox potential of approximately 1.5 V and without SEI film may induce undesirable reactions between the anode, electrolyte, and trace water. The release of gases at $\approx 1.3\text{V}$ (such as H_2 , CO_2 and CH_4 et.al) through electrolyte decomposition poses potential risks of cell failure. Nevertheless, the unconventional

materials and mechanisms of complex niobium tungsten oxides anode can inspire more attention to micrometers sized electrode materials with attractive crystal structures.

3. 2 Micro-nano Hybrid Electrode Materials with Architecture and Kinetic Correlation

Notwithstanding consisting of nanoscale domains, the micro-nano hybrid structure electrode materials are typically micron-sized granular. The design of hybrid electrode materials can reduce the side effects of nanomaterials and ensure higher volumetric energy density. Recently, various micro-nano hybrid structure electrode materials have been developed for high-performance Li batteries. Depending on the combination of micro and nanomaterials, the hybrid electrode materials are categorized as follows: microscale active materials with a nanolayer,¹⁵⁴⁻¹⁵⁶ microscale secondary active materials consisting of nanomaterials,^{157, 158} and microscale porous electrode materials¹⁵⁹⁻¹⁶¹.

3. 2.1 Microscale Active Materials with Nanolayers

The microscale active materials with a nanolayer succeed in protecting the inner active materials, enhancing the conductivity and even energy density.^{162, 163} The nanolayer can be defined as the same as the coating layer, which can be carbon and other conductive materials or a fast ion-conducting surface phase. In general, it is known that the coating has been widely employed in nano electrode materials to enhance the rate property. However, the application of coating can protect the materials from side reactions and enhance the initial coulomb efficiency and ion diffusion on the surface, such strategy in micorscale electrode materials is still hindered by the sluggish ionic transfer in the bulk phase. Therefore, it is suitable for electrode materials with pppropriate crystal structures for fast charging. For instance, the bulk lithium transport of LiFePO_4 is so fast that the charging is ultimately limited by surface adsorption and surface transfer. The bulk LiFePO_4 obtains ultrahigh rate performance by creating the off-stoichiometric layer with high ion mobility, which can enhance the Li^+ diffusion along with a particular (010) facet of the inner bulk. The material synthesis strategy had been to create the coating constituents $\text{LiFe}_{0.9}\text{P}_{0.95}\text{O}_{4-\delta}$ from LiFePO_4 as the nanolayer on the

surface for the rapid transport of Li^+ and electrons. The rate capability of the modified LiFePO_4 is two orders of magnitude higher and equivalent to the full battery within 20 s.¹⁶⁴

Fast charging for the conventional graphite anodes have been hindered by the dendrite formation of metallic lithium caused by the low lithiation voltage (0.08V vs Li/Li^+) and the limited intercalation kinetics. In order to realize the high volumetric energy density and fast charging ability of graphite anode, Kim and co-workers fabricated a micron-sized hybrid anode consisting of an amorphous silicon nanolayer and edge-plane-activated graphite (SEAG).¹⁶⁵ The silicon nanolayer with a safer lithium-alloying potential (0.08V vs Li/Li^+) can prevent the deposition of lithium metal. Besides, the hybrid anode succeeds in enhancing the Li^+ transport and boosting fast charging performance owing to the high specific capacity and shortened the Li^+ diffusion length of the silicon nanolayer¹⁶⁶. Furthermore, the average sizes and tap density of the SEAG are nearly the same as the pristine graphite (**Figure 7a-c**). Under harsh industrial electrode conditions, the composite anode exhibited outstanding initial coulombic efficiency (93.8%) and 1.5 times faster charging than the conventional graphite at ultrahigh current density (10.2 mA cm^{-2} , $1\text{C} = 3.5 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). Such excellent performance highlighted its viability in fast rechargeable high-energy battery applications.

Figure 7. (a) Cross-sectional schematic illustration of the structure and characteristics of SEAG. (b) Particle-size distribution and (c) tap density of pristine graphite and SEAG. Schematic showing the detailed structure and characteristics of (d) RASC-NCM and (e) electrolyte-proof configuration LCNE materials. (f) Schematic diagram of the preparation process of the porous Si, which starts from SiO₂ nanoparticles. (g) SEM images of the obtained micro-sized mesoporous silicon. The inset is the magnified image of microparticles. (h) The specific capacities and voltage profiles of nano-Si, graphite, and p-Si/C at 11 A g⁻¹. a-c) Reproduced with permission.¹⁶⁵ Copyright 2017, Nature Publishing Group. d) Reproduced with permission.¹⁶⁷ Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH. e) Reproduced

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3. 2.2 Microscale Secondary Active Materials Consisting of Nanomaterials

Compared with the nanomaterials, the size of microscale secondary active materials is much larger than its components of nanomaterials without sacrificing the tap density. Furthermore, the micromaterials can reduce the surface area contact with electrolytes, leading to higher coulombic efficiency and a longer lifespan. The microscale secondary active materials have been extensively investigated and mainly include two types: primary particles assembled into micrometer-sized particles^{170, 171} and primary particles embedded in the micrometer-sized matrix¹⁷².

For the primary particles assembled into micrometer-sized particles, the secondary particle electrode material brings high tap density and high rate performance, but design principles should take intergranular and intragranular mechanical cracking during cycling into account¹⁷³. These microcracks existing both between grains and within individual grains not only create mechanical stress within the secondary particles, but also serve as reaction sites with the electrolytes. This results in the formation of a thick solid-electrolyte interphase layer along the surface, consequently hindering the movement of electrons and lithium ions. Therefore, the internal strain caused by state-of-charge heterogeneity and fracture toughening the secondary particle should be effectively dissipates. Du and co-workers fabricated micrometer-sized Ni-rich $\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ (NCM) cathode materials with radially aligned single-crystal primary particles (RASC-NCM) through an improved coprecipitation method.¹⁶⁷ The well-alignment exposed specific (010) plane provided a fast 3D ion diffusion channel from surface to center, remarkably enhancing the Li^+ diffusion coefficient. Besides, the stress by volume variation can also be effectively suppressed by the coordinated volume change between primary particles, significantly prolonging the lifespan of batteries (**Figure 7d**). As a result, the RASC-NCM can deliver a high capability of $152.7 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ at 5C (equal to 1 A g^{-1}), much higher than the commercial NCM (C-NCM, $128.6 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$).

For the primary particles embedded in the micrometer-sized matrix, a well-constructed network for the transmission of electrons and ions can be effectively established. Besides, the matrix as the protect layer can effectively stabilize the electrode–electrolyte interface. The primary particles embedded in the micrometer-sized matrix were also widely developed for the practical application of next-generation high-energy Li batteries. A dendrite-free and stable hierarchical hybrid Li metal anode is demonstrated by Cui and co-workers by encapsulating nanosized Li domains into the Li-ion conductive $\text{Li}_x\text{Si-Li}_2\text{O}$ matrix (**Figure 7e**).¹⁶⁸ There are two properties of the hybrid anode superior to bare Li foil. The first one, the porous matrix of Li-embedded $\text{Li}_x\text{Si-Li}_2\text{O}$ electrode (LCNE) provided the space to buffer large volume change and afforded the additional channels for ion and electron transfer. The second one, compared to the “open-framework” matrix, the hybrid LCNE anode possessed a protective electrolyte-proof surface by embedding nanosized Li within the matrix, which can avoid excess initial side reactions. Benefiting from the above advantages, the hybrid anode exhibited lower overpotential and higher rate capability coupled with the sulfur cathode, especially at high current density ($\sim 600 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ at 6.69 mA cm^{-2}). Xu et al. showed the capability to build a protective matrix layer of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) on both primary and secondary particles of NCM¹⁷⁴. The formation of the high intrinsic conductivity of the PEDOT on both inner and outermost surfaces of the cathode particles enhance charge transfer on the cathode surface and therefore reduces the resistance of materials and eliminate the microcracks, which offers the fast charging and long-term cycling performance.

3. 2.3 Microscale Porous Electrode Materials

The required energy density can be increased by denser and thicker electrode materials, regardless of the active material used. However, due to the restriction of mass transport, it is hard to meet the requirements at higher current densities for a working battery. Fundamentally, the higher load current will lead to the increase of overpotential and insufficient performance of capacity. Porous materials are considered a promising candidate to overcome the limitations arising from high mass

loading electrodes.¹⁷⁵⁻¹⁷⁸ The enhanced electrochemical performance of porous materials derives from multidimensional pores: micropores (< 2 nm) can store ions, mesopores (2-50 nm) can provide fast transport channels for ions, and macropores (>50 nm) can buffer stress caused by the volume change.¹⁷⁹ In general, the pores of electrode materials generally decrease the volumetric storage density. Therefore, the trade-off between porosity: and sufficiently high ionic conductivity provided by contacting area with electrolyte should be considered for optimizing the energy density of fast charging devices. Tailoring the structure and morphology of electrodes to achieve the desired balance between porosity and conductivity. For example, excessive porosity can result in unused or dead spaces that do not contribute to ion transport or electrochemical reactions. This can reduce the overall efficiency of the electrode.

Microscale porous electrode materials with mesoporous or microporous demonstrated satisfactory fast charging performance, whose sizes are similar to the conventional electrode materials. Besides, the packing efficiency is much higher than stacked nanoparticles. In this regard, Kuppan et al. reported a micrometer-sized mesoporous TiO₂ with nano-sized grains as well as pores on the same scale with a facile conduction path. The rate capability of the TiO₂ electrode is dramatically enhanced (107 mA h g⁻¹ at 30 C), which is 5 times better than the commercial TiO₂ powder¹⁸⁰. Furthermore, the packing density of the obtained TiO₂ is 6.6 times higher than TiO₂ nanoparticles.¹⁶⁶ Recently, a spherical micrometer-sized carbon-coated porous Si (p-Si/C) anode with unique porous was proposed and demonstrated excellent electrochemical performance by the method of a microemulsion of silica nanoparticles and magnesiothermic reduction process (**Figure 7f**).¹⁶⁹ In general, the p-Si/C anode exhibits the primary mesoporous silicon well-distributed micrometer-sized secondary particles (**Figure 7g**). The unique fabrication approach endows the Si-based anode with well-aligned architecture and a tap density close to bulk Si particles. The design concept of the Si-based anode makes full use of the advantages of micro/nanostructure, which can effectively accommodate volume change and keep structural stability. Furthermore, the electronic conductivity is substantially

enhanced with the well-distributed carbon coating on the surface and inside the secondary particles. As a result, the Si-based anode demonstrated a very high specific capacity of $\sim 650 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ at 11 A g^{-1} (Figure 7h).

3.3 Microscale Concentration Gradient Structure Electrode Materials for Reliable Fast Charging

Concentration gradient structures in electrode materials for batteries refer to materials that are designed with a gradient in the concentration of lithium ions or other active species within the electrode. Compared with core-shell structure coating, concentration gradient structure electrode materials can overcome the drawbacks such as being unsuitable for large-scale application and the structural mismatch between the core and the shell¹⁸¹. Various efforts have been devoted to developing chemical concentration gradient structure cathode materials, especially for oxide cathodes. Oxide cathodes have been widely investigated and shown a perfect application, including layered nickel-cobalt-manganese oxides, spinel LiM_2O_4 (M = manganese or nickel), and polyanion ($\text{Li}_x\text{Fe}_2(\text{XO}_4)_3$, X=S, Mo, and W) cathodes.^{182, 183} Especially, for Ni-rich layered oxide cathodes, with easier synthesis getting stable highly oxidized $\text{M}^{3+/4+}$ states and better electronic conductivity, have shown more attractive applications which require higher volumetric energy density. However, the disordered transition-metal (TM) Ni/Li-ion and TM ions dissolution leading to structure evolution during the cycling process has restricted their further practical application. Besides, the higher Ni content the more aggravated cation mixing, which induces a higher energy barrier of ions diffusion and lower ionic conductivity. Furthermore, the operation of layered cathodes under high rates and high temperatures leads to accelerated structural degradation and poorer ion migration kinetics.

To address these issues, special core-shell structures of concentration gradient have been employed to obtain micron-sized cathode particles with a high power density and stable service life^{120, 181, 184}. Generally, the chemical concentration gradient cathode materials include surface concentration gradient type¹⁸⁵⁻¹⁸⁷ and full concentration gradient (FCG) type¹⁸⁸⁻¹⁹². Surface concentration gradient

can be considered as the modified conventional core-shell structure (the composition of the shell changes gradually and the core remains unchanged), which can avoid structural mismatch and losing electrical contact between the shell and core during charging and discharging. The FCG structure is the further development of surface gradient, in which the concentration of components in the entire range from the center to the surface changes linearly and without an obvious dividing line between the frontal inner core and the outer shell. Consequently, the FCG structure effectively eliminates structural mismatches, particularly at the interface, thereby bolstering structural integrity and extending the lifespan.

3.3.1 Surface Gradient Structure Cathode Materials

Figure 8. (a) Schematic illustration of the surface gradient structure cathode. (b) SEM results of the structure mismatch at the interface, exhibit a thick gradient layer. (c) EPMA line scan of the lithiated oxide $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.64}\text{Co}_{0.18}\text{Mn}_{0.18}]\text{O}_2$, the gradual concentration changes of Ni, Mn, and Co in the interlayer are clearly evident. (d) Schematic illustration of the structure design of gradient surface Na^+ doping Li-rich material ($0.5\text{Li}_2\text{MnO}_3 \cdot 0.5\text{LiNi}_{1/3}\text{Co}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$). (e) SEM images of micron-sized Li-rich SLR. (f) The initial voltage profiles of pristine and Na^+ doping Li-rich cathode materials. (g) Schematic showing the mechanical structure and characteristics of Ti doping to enhance the storage/cycling stability. (h) High-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) image of NC82-Ti. A clean surface of NC82-Ti with a disordered structure caused by Ti-gradient doping. (i) Galvanostatic charge capacities comparison of NC82-Ti and NC82 paired with Li metal foil at various current densities between 2.8–4.3 V. a-c) Reproduced with permission.¹⁹³ Copyright 2009, Nature Publishing Group. d-f) Reproduced with permission.¹⁹⁴ Copyright 2016, Wiley-VCH. g-i) Reproduced with permission.¹⁹⁵ Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH.

3.3.1 Surface Gradient Structure Cathode Materials

To date, the chemical concentration gradient structure of cathode materials has been identified as one of the effective candidates for optimizing the structure and chemistry of cathode materials.¹⁹⁶⁻²⁰² The pioneer surface concentration gradient structure with an average composition of $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.68}\text{Co}_{0.18}\text{Mn}_{0.18}]\text{O}_2$ was reported by Sun and coworkers, in which the core $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{0.1}]\text{O}_2$ offered high energy density, and the protective layer with decreasing Ni concentration and increasing Mn, Co concentration provides excellent cycle life and safety (**Figure 8a-c**).¹⁹³ However, it is important to note that the efficiency of ion and electron transfer is limited by the thick gradient layer (up to 2 μm) and the interface structure mismatch (**Figure 8b**). Recently, surface gradient doping structures with thinner layers have been demonstrated to enhance the ion and electrical conductivity at the surface by building stable and fast transmission pathways. Guo and co-workers reported improved kinetics of micron-sized Li-rich oxide cathode through gradient surface Na^+ doping¹⁹⁴

(Figure 8d-f). As demonstrated in **Figure 8f**, the higher charge capacity of gradient surface Na⁺ doped Li-rich materials (SLR) than pristine Li-rich material (PLR) below 4.4 V, indicating the easier diffusion of Li⁺ in the layered structure of SLR. Besides, compared with the PLR, the SLR stabilized the structure by pinning effect, promoting the Li-ion diffusion, and enhancing ionic and electronic conductivity, which is beneficial to superior cycling stability and rate performance.

Additionally, Pan pointed out that the key to issues of high-Ni cathode lies in surface instability. Specifically, the unstable surface is related to the NiO-like rock-salt phase and surface Li₂CO₃ caused by reactions between the high reactive Ni³⁺ with CO₂/H₂O in the air¹⁹⁵. As a result, the LiNi_{0.8}Co_{0.2}O₂ with Ti-gradient doping (NC82-Ti) showed an unprecedentedly clean surface and a Li/Ni-exchange disordered layered phase (**Figure 8g-i**). Interestingly, there is a continuous layered structure induced by gradient Ti doping on the very near surface area, and no secondary phase on the particle surface. Owing to charge balance, the surface gradient Ti doping increases the Ni²⁺ and induces more Li/Ni sites. More importantly, the binding energies for surface and internal oxygen atoms increase and form a more stable O²⁻ framework, inducing a uniquely clean and stable surface. Besides, Li slab exhibits a negligible shrink (0.026%), and does not affect the fast ion diffusion. Consequently, the NC82-Ti delivered excellent cycling stability (capacity retention of 95.55% after 200 cycles at 1C and 25 °C, and 96.37% after 100 cycles at 1C and 45 °C) and unprecedented rate performance (146 mA h g⁻¹ at 20 C, 1C =200 mA h g⁻¹) between 2.8-4.3 V. In addition, the strategy could be widely used in other electrode materials with different transition metal compositions, and effectively improve the reliable fast charging of electrode materials.

3.3.2 FCG Synergistic Structure Cathode Materials

Unfortunately, there is no report for micrometer-sized bulk FCG cathodes with the enhanced rate capacity. A variety of functional cathodes with synergistic FCG structures have been developed for fast charging batteries. For instance, the unique micron-sized secondary active materials consisting of FCG primary grains could lead to high volumetric energy density, structural stability, and fast ionic

diffusion, which will unlock new strategies to meet the needs of the micrometer-sized fast charging batteries.^{181, 203, 204} Sun and co-workers developed micron-sized $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.60}\text{Co}_{0.15}\text{Mn}_{0.25}]\text{O}_2$ secondary particles, consisting of FCG Ni and Co ions at fixed Mn content (FCG-Mn-F) throughout the primary grains (**Figure 9a**)²⁰⁵. For the primary FCG-Mn-F particle, the gradual increase of Co concentration from the center to the surface can enhance the electronic conductivity (**Figure 9b**). Meanwhile, the higher capacity is provided by the linear decreased concentration of Ni from center to surface. Besides, the micrometer-sized secondary FCG-Mn-F cathode with the limited contact surface with electrolyte induces excellent cycle stability (capacity retention of 70.3% after 1000 cycles at 55 °C). Benefiting from the advanced synergistic microstructure and compositional distribution, the hybrid cathode exhibits a higher rate capacity and thermal stability than the conventional composition (CC) $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.60}\text{Co}_{0.15}\text{Mn}_{0.25}]\text{O}_2$. Based on the development of synergistic structure system cathodes, a highly stable synergistic structure $\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ cathode with nickel oxidation state FCG structure in primary particles and inner pores in secondary particles was developed via exploiting polystyrene beads (PSB-NCM) cluster incorporated coprecipitation method by Park and co-workers (**Figure 9c-e**).²⁰⁶ Interestingly, most unstable trivalent nickel ions were reduced to the stable divalent nickel ions during the annealing process, which induces the migration of tetravalent manganese and trivalent cobalt ions from the surface to the center to maintain charge neutrality. The surface of FCG primary particles with divalent nickel ions provides structural stability by suppressing cation disorder. Besides, the inner pore of secondary particles could improve wettability with electrolytes and act as buffer space to forestall volume change. Excitedly, although the porous PSB-NCM cathodes have a lower powder tap density, the value of volumetric energy density was comparable and still higher than pristine NCM. The synergistic structure cathode presented a higher discharge specific capacity of 140 mA h g⁻¹ at a rate of 10 C. Meanwhile, compared with the NCM sample showed poor capacity retention of $\approx 67\%$ for 250 cycles at 1C, the PSB-NCM achieved better discharge capacity retention of $\approx 86\%$ for 250 cycles and enhanced thermal stability.

Figure 9. (a) Cross-sectional SEM and electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) mapping of Ni, Co, and Mn within an FCG structure primary FCG–Mn–F grain (left), TEM image and the corresponding electron diffraction pattern of a single FCG–Mn–F primary particle, showing the crystallographic alignment of the primary particle in the radial direction and Li-ion diffusion channel (right). (b) The integrated atomic ratio of transition metals as a function of distance from the center of the particle for lithiated FCG Mn–F electrode. (c) Illustrations of the gradient nickel oxidation state PSB-NCM, showing the difference between the surface gradient of nickel oxidation state and transition metal concentration. The detailed structure and characteristics of the FCG PSB-NCM primary particles: (d)

STEM image of the well-preserved surface layer and (e) Ni-L edge recorded in the surface of the primary particle. (f) Representative hemisphere image showing the detailed structure and characteristics of FCG RAHC secondary cathode. (g-h) The detailed charge-discharge curves for (g) C/Bulk and (h) C/RAHC full sodium-ion cells, with formation curves (0.1, 0.2 C-rate); cutoff: 1.5–3.9 V, current density: 15 mA g⁻¹ (0.1 C-rate, 1 cycle), 30 mA g⁻¹ (0.2 C-rate, 2 cycles) and 75 mA g⁻¹ (0.5 C-rate, 300 cycles). a, b) Reproduced with permission.²⁰⁵ Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society. c-e) Reproduced with permission.²⁰⁶ Copyright 2017, Wiley-VCH. f-h) Reproduced with permission.²⁰⁷ Copyright 2015, Nature Publishing Group.

The FCG Synergistic Structure merges the advantages of the fast charging and prolonged lifespan, providing a new idea and method for high-energy and reliable electrode materials for batteries. Beyond the application in the field of Li batteries, Sun group developed a highly dense secondary sodium cathode consisting of FCG radially aligned hierarchical columnar structure (RAHC) primary grain (**Figure 9f**). Given this new concept design, the functional cathode has a gradient composition from Ni-rich core Na[Ni_{0.75}Co_{0.02}Mn_{0.23}]O₂ to the Mn-rich surface Na[Ni_{0.58}Co_{0.06}Mn_{0.36}]O₂.²⁰⁷ The Ni-rich core supported by Ni^{3+/4+} redox exhibited more capacity and the Mn-rich shell provided high stability (**Figure 9g-h**). Benefitting from the directed fast channels for Na⁺ ion diffusion and more Ni³⁺ along with columnar structure particles, the RAHC cathode delivers a high specific capacity of 127.3 mA h g⁻¹ under 10 C rate. A capacity retention of 80% (125mAhg⁻¹) during 300 cycles in combination with a hard carbon anode. In addition, various electrode materials with synergistic structures and high tapped density have been investigated for high power density batteries.²⁰⁸

4. Microscale Fast Charging Electrode Materials in Engineering Design

Aforementioned state-of-the-art the emerging micronization electrode materials with nanoscale contributions at active materials level and points out the materials design from atomic to structure to boosting the high energy and reliable fast charging electrode materials. Electrochemical performance is affected by the contribution of both electrons and ionics transport systems at multi-scal. Optimizing

active materials alone does not solve all problems related to fast charging, especially for commercial thick electrodes²⁰⁹. Hence, aiming to reduce electron/ion transport barriers and tuning electrode parameters through architecture design at electrode level is essential. 3D microscale hybrid electrode materials and microscale low-tortuosity electrode materials, focusing on carrier transport network construction and optimization are illustrated in this section.

4.1 3D Microscale Hybrid Electrode Materials

Electrode materials hold the key to primary advantages in fast charging batteries, depending on the migration rate of ions and electrons throughout the whole electrode. A series of microscale 3D hybrid electrode materials have been assembled and exhibited excellent fast charging performance.²¹⁰⁻²¹⁴ Ordinarily, the hybrid electrodes contain a 3D interconnected network for efficient transport channels of both charge and ions. The hybrid electrodes can break through the limitations of the traditional depth-limited planar current collector and can achieve high mass loading of running. The traditional electrode is fabricated by coating a planar current collector, with a slurry containing the active materials, binder, and conductive agent. The electrons must transfer from active particle to active particle until they reach the current collector, and the poor kinetics at interparticle boundaries are the major limitations for fast charging. Especially for a thick electrode, only part of active materials can realize the full application for energy storage and conversion, leading to a lower power density. In contrast, the high conductive 3D networks can alleviate thick electrode polarization and prolong the service life, especially at high rates.

Here, we focus on the microscale 3D hosts with a continuous conductive network and a full open-cell structure, which is beneficial for electron and ion transport in thick electrodes. The most-reported 3D scaffolds have a wide pore size range from several to hundreds of micrometers, which have a high specific surface area and ensure high active materials mass loading. Besides, the intrinsic structural integrity of the architectures has the function of buffer volume changes, especially for alloy- or conversion-type materials.²¹⁵ More specifically, the 3D scaffolds are generally not active materials

and do not participate in charge storage, which should be lightweight, high intensity, and ensure energy density.^{104, 216-219} According to the type of materials of conductive scaffolds they can be divided into metal-based and carbon-based frameworks.

Figure 10. (a) Schematic illustration of Li behavior in the metal-based dendrite-free 3D microscale hybrid composite anode. (b) Comparison of Nyquist plot of the impedance spectra of the hybrid anode and the bare Li anode in symmetric cells at a current density of 1 mA cm⁻², the lower resistance of the hybrid anode exhibited better electrode stability and easier Li stripping/plating kinetics. (c) Rate performances of the 3D hybrid and the bare Li electrode paired with LTO at different current densities. (d-f) Surface and cross-section SEM images of the hybrid anode with LTO electrode after 100 cycles

at various rates, showing a stable electrode structure and interface. a-f) Reproduced with permission.²²⁰ Copyright 2017, Wiley-VCH.

4.1.1 Metal-based Frameworks

Metal-based frameworks, such as nickel (Ni)-based, copper (Cu)-based, titanium (Ti)-based, etc. al., usually have satisfactory mechanical strength, open structure, structural stability, and electronic conductivity, which are essential for high-performance batteries.²²¹ The metal-based framework and Li metal composite anode with different properties were widely investigated to regulate the Li plating and stripping in rechargeable Li metal batteries. Zhang and co-workers demonstrated a 3D microscale hybrid anode with a Ni-based host for storing Li by thermal infusion method, in which the manufacturing process is simple and without impurities (**Figure 10a**).²²⁰ The 3D hybrid anode with the Ni foam host not only reduces the local current density but also decreases the surface energy with electrolytes. Besides, the Ni foam with excellent mechanical strength can effectively buffer the infinite volume changes of Li metal anode. Compared with the bare Li foil anode, the dendrite-free hybrid anode can run stable at a high current density of 5 mA cm^{-2} and with lower resistance for more than 100 cycles (**Figure 10b**). In a full cell system matched with the hybrid anode, both LFP and LTO cathode demonstrated better rate capacity, longer lifespan, and lower interfacial resistance at different rates (**Figure 10c**). The surface and cross-section of the composite Li metal anode exhibited a stable thickness of $\sim 800 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ without dendrite growth after 100cycles (**Figure 10d-f**). Similarly, the metal-based host acts as the conductive framework for filling the S cathode, can increase the electrical conductivity, and further improve the electrochemical performance, especially at high charge and discharge rates.²²² However, it should be noted that the metal-based framework with high density and a complicated package cannot meet the requirement of high energy density batteries. Therefore, research associated with lightweight and high-intensity metal-based frameworks could contribute to optimizing the energy density of fast-charging devices.

Figure 11. (a) Schematics comparing the structures of the 3D hybrid $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5/\text{HGF-2.0}$ electrode and the traditional slurry-based $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5/\text{G}$ composite electrode. (b, c) Comparison of Nyquist plots and the ionic resistance, the 3D hybrid $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5/\text{HGF-2.0}$ electrode with the optimal porosity and kinetic properties. (d) Comparison of specific capacity retention as a function of mass loading for three

different electrodes at the rate of 10 C. (e) Translation of specific capacities at various current densities for the Nb₂O₅/HGF-2.0 electrode with mass loadings of 1 and 11 mg cm⁻², and the hybrid electrode showed excellent performance with high mass loading. a-e) Reproduced with permission.²²³ Copyright 2017, American Association for the Advancement of Science.

4.1.2 Carbon-based 3D Frameworks

In the past couple of decades, carbon-based materials have been widely used in various fields due to their inherent characteristics, such as high electrical conductivity, extremely light, high mechanical, low heat expansion coefficient, and thermal stability.²²⁴⁻²²⁶ The carbon-based 3D frameworks, such as carbon fiber-based architecture, carbon nanotubes-based architecture, graphene-based architecture biomass-based carbon architecture, and their composites, play a significant role in this context.²²⁷⁻²³¹ Compared with the metal-based framework, the lower density of carbon-based frameworks ensures higher active materials loading and higher gravimetric energy density. Besides, the freestanding metal-free carbon-based framework is employed as the current collector, which has no need binder and conductive agents. The 3D hybrid electrodes with a continuous conductive network and appropriate porosity ensure sufficient charge and ions transfer, which is beneficial for reaching the full performance potential of active materials in thick and high mass loading electrodes. For instance, a conductive 3D holey graphene framework (3D-HCG) loaded with the orthorhombic form of Nb₂O₅ (T-Nb₂O₅) as a hybrid electrode has been reported by Duan and co-workers (**Figure 11a**).²²³ T-Nb₂O₅ with inherent ultra-high-rate performance was chosen to evaluate the contribution of the hybrid electrode design to the rate performance. For the hybrid electrode, the overall controlling step is decided by ion and electronic transport on the surface rather than inside the active T-Nb₂O₅. Besides, the hybrid electrodes with varying pore sizes were prepared by a novel two-step method without affecting the overall structure to probe the impact of the porosity on the electrochemical performance. The observed results showed the hybrid electrode with nanopores (0~2.7 nm) had lower interfacial charge transfer/ion resistance (**Figure 11 b-c**), higher specific capacity, and rate

performance, which attributed to the unique structure and efficient ion transport overall the 3D electrodes. More importantly, the effect of mass loading on electrode performance was also investigated. As is known, the high mass loading electrode is vitally important to the practical application of high energy density and high-power density electrochemical batteries. Compared with the 3D porous Nb₂O₅/GF with no in-plane nanopores and Nb₂O₅/G with a randomly stacked graphene network, the 3D-HCG composite Nb₂O₅/HGF-2.0 with optimized nanopores delivered a much better rate capacity without obvious decrease, even with increasing mass loading. Specifically, due to the optimized ions and charge transport kinetics, the 3D hybrid Nb₂O₅/HGF-2.0 electrode delivered higher capacity retention for mass loading from 1 to 11 mg cm⁻² at rates of 10 C (**Figure 11 d-e**). As introduced above, 3D framework provides an effective way to generate a controllable and continuous transport network inside the electrode composites to achieve higher energy and power densities. For future studies, the manufacturing cost and scalability need be further optimized to bridge the gap between laboratory and industrial applications.

4.2 Microscale Low-tortuosity Electrode Materials

The tortuosity is recognized as one of the critical parameters that determine the efficiency and reliability of mass transport and charge transfer.²³²⁻²³⁴ Exaggerative tortuosity can bring about extending ion transmission path or ion depletion and account for unsatisfactory rate capacity, especially in the fast charging process.^{235, 236} As the tortuosity of electrodes is difficult to determine and quantify, various calculation approaches have been developed to ascertain the correlation between the tortuosity and battery performance.^{108, 237-239} Understanding the correlation is helpful to design low-tortuosity electrode materials. In brief, reducing the tortuosity of the electrode is an effective measure to accelerate the kinetics of the electrode process, particularly for thick electrodes. The traditional electrode fabrication process for batteries involves high-pressure calendaring to densify electrodes and improve electrical contact.²⁴⁰ For this kind of electrode, the energy density increases with electrode density and thickness. However, it may exacerbate tortuosity and concentration

gradient resistance in a certain transport direction at the electrode level.^{45, 241} Beyond the critical threshold of charge/discharge rate, electronic conductivity and charge transfer in electrode materials cease to be the limiting factors, with ion transport within the electrode becoming the primary rate-determining process.^{242, 243} As is known, the full potential capacity of electrode materials can be fully utilized only when the active materials have an adequate supply of ions and appropriate charge transport resistance. Simultaneously, it can mitigate security issues, including the formation of Li dendrites and thermal runaway incidents.²⁴⁴ Thus, electrode materials with low tortuosity have been employed to improve the rate capability without sacrificing energy density.^{28, 29, 245-247} Various methods have been developed to fabricate low tortuosity electrode materials, such as applying external magnetic field alignment, directional freeze-casting, biomass-derived low tortuosity host, et. al.

4.2.1 Low-tortuosity Electrodes With Magnetized Additives for Fast Charging

Magnetized additives are frequently employed as the auxiliary component to construct electrode materials with ordered directionally and reduced tortuosity.¹¹⁷ Billaud and coworkers reported the functionalization of well-aligned microscale graphite flakes anode with a low concentration of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs). The SPIONs demonstrated a sensitive magnetic response under 100 mT (**Figure 12a**).²⁴⁸ Compared with the traditional design, the well-aligned micron-sized graphite flakes electrode presented four times less tortuosity. As a result, ordered porous structures can significantly reduce the ion transport distance in the ultrathick (~200 μm) and high mass loading (~10 mg cm^{-2}) electrodes (**Figure 12b**). Benefiting from the low tortuosity and enhanced ion transport kinetics, the resulting electrode demonstrated 3 times increased capacity at high rates compared to the random configuration (**Figure 12c**). Thus, it is anticipated to enhance the practical fast charging performance.

Figure 12. Magnetic alignment electrode materials. (a) Schematic diagram and morphology of the aligned microscale graphite flakes functionalization with Fe₃O₄ and packing structure. (b) The Cross-sectional SEM images of the well-aligned electrodes. (c) Evolution of the specific charge and overpotential at various rates. (d-e) The low tortuosity electrode fabrication process is based on the magnetic alignment of nanorods. Cross-sectional (f) and top view (g) of the low-tortuosity LCO electrodes with anisotropic pore channels. (h) Rate performances of 310-μm-thick LCO electrodes with 39–42% pore channels. a-c) Reproduced with permission.²⁴⁸ Copyright 2016, Nature Publishing Group. d-h) Reproduced with permission.²⁴⁹ Copyright 2016, Nature Publishing Group.

Magnetized nylon rods and oil-based ferrofluid as additives for creating ordered ion transport networks were introduced during the electrode fabrication process by Chiang and co-workers.²⁴⁹ As

illustrated in **Figure 12d**, with the nylon rods as a pore-forming additive, to be specific, the nylon rods are arranged regularly under the action of a magnetic field in the composite electrode. After sacrificing the nylon and binder through high-temperature sintering, the free-standing low tortuosity porous composite electrode can be obtained. As a result, the oriented pores along the thickness direction and throughout the entire electrode provided electrode thickness independent fast ion transport channels (**Figure 12e-g**). Benefiting from the unique structure, the thick electrode (~100 μm) exhibited almost all of the full potential capacity. Meanwhile, the amount of total porosity in the aligned pore channels and microporous matrix was investigated to optimize the tortuosity and rate performance (**Figure 12h**). Furthermore, the rate performance of sintered LiCoO_2 cathode delivered about 3 times higher capacity of the commercial batteries at 2 C (1 C=140 mA h g^{-1}). However, whether the performance improvement at the rate of 1-2 C could meet the requirement of fast charging is worthy of further study. Moreover, the concentration of magnetized additives should be strictly controlled to avoid affecting electrochemical performance.

4.2.2 Directional Freeze-casting Low-tortuosity Electrode for Fast Charging

Freeze-casting technique, also known as ice template, has been widely used to fabricate long-range aligned porous materials without byproducts and impurities.²⁵⁰⁻²⁵⁴ Most importantly, the porous structures can be regulated by freeze-casting to obtain the optimal charge transport properties throughout the electrode materials. It is of great significance in increasing the efficient charge transfer channels.²⁵⁵⁻²⁵⁷ The well-aligned channels bring about the shortened transfer distance and buffer the volume change during cycling, especially under high mass loading.^{253, 258-260} The charge transfer (including ion and electron) in the electrode is the rate-limiting factor, especially in ultrathick electrodes²⁶¹. As demonstrated in **Figure 13a-b**, a low-tortuosity hybrid electrode containing $\text{LiFe}_{0.7}\text{Mn}_{0.3}\text{PO}_4$ nanoplates (LFMP NPs) and graphene was fabricated by the freeze-casting method by Zhao and coworkers.²⁶² The well-aligned electrode with vertical channels facilitates efficient ion transfer. The electrode demonstrated a higher capacity, which is 2.5 times higher than that of the

randomly structured electrode. Besides, the sandwich framework provided the “plate-on-sheet” contact between LFMP NPs and graphene wall, which induces robust electron transfer pathways even at high current density. As a result, the vertical-channel sandwich electrodes (LFMP-IGF) demonstrate the enhanced kinetics of active materials and a superior rate capability (0.2 C–20 C) with ultrahigh mass loading of about 21.2 mg cm⁻² (**Figure 13c-d**). Compared with typical slurry-casted electrodes, the low tortuosity electrode demonstrated a much more remarkable improvement in the areal capacity. As shown in **Figure 13e-f**, the LFMP-IGF with two different levels of mass loading (from 11 to 21.2 mg cm⁻²) exhibited less than 10% specific capacity decrease at each corresponding C-rate. Compared with the representative slurry-casted current collectors, the LFMP-IGF has shown an obvious advantage of lower decay with increasing C-rates.

Figure 13. Directional freeze-casting electrode materials. For Li metal anode. (a) The low tortuosity electrode fabrication process is based on the directional freeze-casting method. (b) Illustration of Li-

ion transfer and electrolyte diffusion in LFMP-IGF with low tortuosity channels and traditional structure. (c-d) The improved rate capacity at various rates induced by the low tortuosity structure. (e-f) Comparison of specific capacity of the low-tortuosity electrode and the reported research-level cathodes. (g) Schematic of the effect of tortuosity on the behavior of Li plating/stripping. (h) The CE of Li anodes with different tortuosity at a high current density and capacity (5 mA cm^{-2} , 5 mA h cm^{-2}). (i) Evolution of the rate capability and long-term cycling performances of LFP cells with different anodes. a-f) Reproduced with permission.²⁶² Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH. g-i) Reproduced with permission.²⁶³ Copyright 2020, Elsevier.

Beyond the application in the field of Li-ion batteries, the freeze-casting technique was widely used to fabricate the low tortuosity host for Li-metal,^{264, 265} $\text{S}^{266-269}$ and other high capacity electrode materials. Recently, the effect of tortuosity on Li reversible deposition behavior was made a detailed investigation by Cui and coworkers.²⁶³ Firstly, series tortuosity and low-tortuosity vertically aligned graphene oxide (rGo) hosts were performed by the freeze-casting method. The author confirmed that there is a clear relationship between the tortuosity of the host and the morphology of Li metal anode, further connected to a series of electrochemical performances (**Figure 13g**). In detail, the uneven gradient of ion concentration and electrochemical reaction in high tortuosity electrodes induce Li dendrite growth on the top preferentially, further blocking the ion transfer channels and decreasing the electrochemical performance. On the contrary, the low-tortuosity, vertically aligned rGo/Li hybrid electrode demonstrated a high coulomb efficiency ($\sim 99.08\%$) and a dendrite-free surface under high-capacity and high-current-density (5 mA h cm^{-2} , 5 mA cm^{-2}) (**Figure 13h-i**). Besides, the tortuosity of the rGo host can be regulated by the freeze-casting technique, which offers a pathway toward the implementation of high-safety and high-performance Li metal batteries.

4.2.3 Bio-derived Low-tortuosity Electrode Scaffold for Fast Charging

The low tortuosity channels for long-distance transport transporting water and ions from roots and stems to leaves exist widely in the xylem of the land plants²⁷⁰⁻²⁷² (**Figure 14a**). Inspired by the

unique structure, various low-tortuosity electrodes have been incorporated with the naturally low tortuosity transport channels.²⁷³⁻²⁷⁶ Until now, a series of wood-derived low tortuosity carbon hosts with robust mechanical properties and superior charge transfer performance has been demonstrated and widely used in Li-ion, Li metal, Li-sulfur, and beyond.^{272, 276-282}

Figure 14. Biomass-derived low tortuosity electrode materials. (a) The photograph and the illustration of low tortuosity channels for long-distance transport transporting water and ions in wood.

(b) Schematics illustrating of preparation of the wood-derived low tortuosity LFP-CF electrode and the fast charge in the LFP-CF cell during charge/discharge.

(c) Schematic of material design and fabrication process of the Li metal-based hybrid anode derived from C-wood.

(d) Schematic illustration and the rate performance of the Li-S cell with the PEO gel composite electrolyte.

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b) Reproduced with permission.²⁷⁹ Copyright 2017, Wiley-VCH.

c, d) Reproduced with permission.²⁸¹ Copyright 2017, NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES.

In the field of Li-ion batteries, the ultrathick electrode was fabricated by infiltrating LFP into the anisotropic multichannel of wood-derived carbon framework (CF).²⁷⁹ The low-tortuosity channels are retained during the sintering treatment, which endows the ion and electron fast transmission kinetics for better rate performance (**Figure 14b**). As a result, the hybrid LFP-CF electrode materials demonstrated a high areal capacity (7.6 mA h cm^{-2}) with a high mass loading (60 mg cm^{-2}), which is a great improvement over the conventional LFP electrode. Besides, the low-tortuosity vertical microchannels decorated with lithiophilic ZnO acting as a host for Li metal anode can buffer the volume change and present a homogeneous contact with Li-ions during the Li plating/stripping process (**Figure 14c**).²⁸¹ Benefiting from the low-tortuosity structure, compared with the bare Li metal anode, the Li/C-wood hybrid electrodes could deliver a lower overpotential and better cycling performance at a high current density of $3 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Furthermore, as is demonstrated in **Figure 14d**, the vertically aligned 3D wood-derived materials filled with high conductive rGO have been reported as a host for the high sulfur mass loadings cathode.²⁷⁸ The low-tortuosity structure reduced ion transport distance and enabled powerful electronic transport. Consequently, the hybrid S cathode demonstrated a high areal capacity ($15.2 \text{ mA h cm}^{-2}$) with a mass loading of 21.3 mg cm^{-2} . The unique wood-derived low-tortuosity materials can also be applied to other electrode materials, which can realize an ultrahigh energy density with unprecedented rate performance. Furthermore, benefiting from abundant, sustainable, and biodegradable, various low-tortuosity electrode materials derived from natural woods and other biomaterials will be promising candidates for high energy/power density batteries.

As introduced above, microscale low-tortuosity electrode materials provide a facile way to control of the ionic transfer inside the composite electrode. Low-tortuosity materials can help achieve uniform utilization by facilitating even ion transport throughout the electrode and minimize overpotential, leading to higher efficiency over the electrochemical reaction on the electrode-level. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that there is still a considerable journey ahead before

their practical applications can be realized. First, low-tortuosity materials may be less mechanically robust, which can lead to structural degradation or even failure of the battery under stress conditions. Second, some low-tortuosity electrode materials can be more expensive to manufacture or less readily available compared to traditional electrode materials, which can impact the cost-effectiveness and scalability of Li-ion battery production. Despite these facts, from a scientific point of view, they are particularly valuable in the development of microscale fast charging electrode materials.

5. Advanced Self-healing Functional Microscale Electrode Design for Robust Fast Charging

Enabling fast charging requires a comprehensive evaluation of battery performance. Apart from the rate capability and high energy density, ensuring the robust cycling stability of batteries intended for practical applications is of paramount importance²⁸³, especially for the high-capacity alloy- and conversion-type electrode materials, such as Si,²⁸⁴ Li,²⁸⁵ P,²⁸⁶ Al²⁸⁷ and S²⁸⁸. Cracking and fracture of electrode materials caused by diffusion induced stress (DIS) and massive anisotropic volume changes under high charge and discharge rates have been identified as one of the main reasons for the insufficient cycle life and capacity of batteries.^{289, 290}

Specifically, compared with the insertion-type electrode materials that undergo small volume changes (< 10%), the high-capacity electrochemistry involves multielectron redox and drastic phase transfer and is more likely to lead to structural collapse.¹⁴ The generation of the microcracks can cause electrical contact failure and increased kinetic barriers, which can negatively impact electrochemical performance and cell safety. In addition, the new surface created by microcracks will cause the generation of a new solid electrolyte interface,²⁹¹ along with the irreversible capacity loss by consuming Li ions and electrolytes (**Figure 15**). Adopting various nanomaterials below the critical cracking/fracture size can alleviate the fracture of electrode materials. However, it will bring about serious issues of nano-sized materials, such as low coulombic efficiency and unsatisfactory volumetric energy density. Electrode materials endowed with self-healing characteristics have been extensively researched as a promising solution for utilizing bulk electrode materials in fast-charging

batteries, aiming to extend their cycle life.²⁹²⁻²⁹⁵ Self-healing electrode materials can spontaneously repair or avoid cracking and fracture of particles and electrodes, further enhancing durability and prolonging service life.²⁹⁶⁻²⁹⁹ To date, self-healing materials developed for energy storage and conversion can be divided into intrinsic self-healing liquid anodes and self-healing ion-conducting binder prolonging the service life of high capacity anodes.

Pulverization

Pulverization

Repeated SEI generation

Figure 15. Fundamental problems concerning conventional bulk high-capacity battery materials: huge volume expansion/shrink during lithiation and delithiation causing pulverization, delamination and an unstable SEI layer. Reproduced with permission.³⁰⁰ Copyright 2020, Royal Society of Chemistry.

5.1 Self-healing Liquid Metal Metals Enhance High-capacity Fast Charging

Liquid alloy additive for high capacity alloy- and conversion-type electrode materials:

Liquidity endows LMA electrodes not only with superior charge transfer kinetics but also non-cracking or dendrite-free during the charge/discharge process, bringing high-rate capacity and

safety.³⁰¹⁻³⁰⁵ Besides, the liquid-liquid electrode-electrolyte interfaces protect LMA batteries from the degradation mechanisms of electrode damage or fracture, thus giving them unprecedented service life. Furthermore, the superior electronic conductivity ($>1 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) endows the fast charging application. Gallium (Ga) with a low melting point (29 °C) was first used as the self-healing cathode in Li batteries by Deshpande and co-workers.³⁰⁶ A reversible solid-liquid transition occurs during lithiation and delithiation of Ga, and the cracks formed during lithiation process can be healed drastically in the subsequent delithiation process. Deshpande first demonstrated the concept of self-healing electrodes by using LMA. To date, various LMA have been used in intelligent energy storage devices, such as Ga-Sn, Ga-In, Na-K, Na-Cs, and their composite. Inspired by the concept, the eutectic Ga-In alloy system was proposed for room temperature liquid metal batteries (RT-LMB).³⁰⁷ The Ga-In alloy has a low eutectic melting temperature (15°C) and high theoretical capacities for both Li and Na. The formation of dendrite and the caused fracture after Li or sodium ions intercalated will self-heal during the extraction process (**Figure 16a**)³⁰⁷. Besides, the fast diffusion of ions in the liquid metal (LM) nanoparticles-carbon-binder system allows fast electron and ionic transport, leading to an outstanding rate capacity. Although the size of the Ga-In alloy is at the nano-level, the comprehensive study of electrochemistry and phase transformation mechanism of RT-LMB guide realizing future practical liquid alloy-based electrode systems. However, the liquid metal nanoparticles via super ultrasonication carries the risk of agglomeration and failure during the cycle as the agglomeration irreversibility of nanomaterials.

Figure 16. (a) Schematics of the electrode design and working mechanism for bulk liquid metal and self-healing LMNP system. (b) Configuration of a cell composed of microscale self-healing a liquid Na-K anode, in which the liquid anode was embedded in the porous current collector. (c) Cathode host dependence of liquid Na-K anode. (d) Schematic diagram of hybrid-cation battery working mechanism, in which the two cations react on both sides synchronously. (e) Rate capacity and coulomb efficiency of the hybrid-cation battery with NMC cathode and liquid Na-K anode. a) Reproduced with permission.³⁰⁷ Copyright 2018, Wiley-VCH. b, c) Reproduced with permission.³⁰⁸

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Self-healing Liquid Metal Metals: Na-K alloy is one of the intrinsically self-healing liquid alloys, which is liquid in a wide range (9.2-58.2 wt.%) of sodium at 25°C. The dendrite-free Na-K anode delivers a high specific capacity of 1366 mA h g⁻¹, which is the ideal alternative to Li metal anode. Besides, the Na-K alloy is chemically stable toward the standard liquid-carbonate electrolyte.³¹⁰ Therefore, the dendrite-free Na-K alloy demonstrates the ability of fast charge and discharge at room temperature (**Figure 16b**). However, the charge carrier working mechanism is dependent on the types of cathode material (**Figure 16c**). Up to now, there are few Na- or K-ion battery cathode materials that can deliver stably large capacity.³⁰⁸ Recently, Yu and coworkers proposed a ternary hybrid-cation liquid metal battery.³⁰⁹ Specifically, a Li-ion LiNi_{1/3}Mn_{1/3}Co_{1/3}O₂ (NCM) cathode is successfully coupled with the liquid eutectic Na-K anode in a hybrid electrolyte containing both K and Li-ion, which inherit advantages of both dendrite-free liquid eutectic Na-K alloy and high capacity Li batteries (**Figure 16d**). Especially, the eutectic Na-K alloy anode is fixed within porous graphitic carbon fiber paper to avoid turbulence. Interestingly, the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) result showed that the chemical reaction kinetics at the surface of Na-K much was faster than the Li metal anode, which induces a better rate capacity. As a result, the hybrid-cation battery system delivered a high stable coulombic efficiency for more than 500 cycles at 1C (1C =150 mA h g⁻¹). Besides, the Na-K alloy anode also delivered a higher rate capacity comparable to Li metal anode, showing the lower transport kinetics of the mix-ion interface (**Figure 16e**). However, it should be noticed that the rigorous package of LMA electrodes should be taken seriously to prohibit the safety issues caused by liquidity.

5.2 Self-Healing Ion-Conducting Binder Prolong the Service Life of Fast Charging

In theory, the microscale electrode coated with a layer of self-healing polymer (SHP) can automatically repair the cracking and fracture, thereby maintaining electrical contact between the

broken particles.³¹¹⁻³¹⁵ Fundamentally, the mechanism of SHPs is based on the instruction of weak chemical bonds in the chains, such as hydrogen bonds and S-S bonds. These broken bonds could reformat the cracked interfaces by the supramolecular assembly process. Typically, the healing process lasts a few minutes to hours. External stimulus, such as heat and catalysis, is always used to speed up the restructuring process. Silicon microparticle (SiMP) with higher volumetric energy density is a promising anode for practical industrial applications. However, its commercialization has been impeded by the cracking and deteriorating electrochemical performance caused by infinite volume changes.

Figure 17. (a) Design and configuration of the self-healing electrode. Scheme 1: electrical contact failure of conventional Si induced by cracking on particles. Scheme 2: the maintaining of electrical contact between the broken particles in the self-healing electrode. (b) Chemical structure of the SHP.

Magenta lines, polymer backbones; light-blue and dark-blue boxes, hydrogen-bonding sites. (c) Schematic of 3D self-healing design Si electrodes with the spatial distribution of self-healing polymer into silicon electrodes and the corresponding SEM images. (d) Schematic illustration of the SiMP electrode with SHP-PEG, (i) the dynamic hydrogen bonding enables the self-healing ability and promotes good adhesion by interaction with hydroxyl groups on the surface of Si microparticles, ii) Li ion conduction facilitated by PEG group. a, b) Reproduced with permission.³¹⁶ Copyright 2013, Nature Publishing Group. c) Reproduced with permission.³¹⁷ Copyright 2015, Wiley-VCH. d) Reproduced with permission.³¹⁸ Copyright 2018, Wiley-VCH.

To overcome this challenge, a self-healing SiMP ($\sim 3-8 \mu\text{m}$) anode coated with a thin layer of the hydrogen-bond-directed polymer was demonstrated by Wang and coworkers.³¹⁶ The functional coating with self-healing and elastic properties enables the SiMP to maintain electrical contact and spontaneously heal the fractures caused by volumetric expansion (**Figure 17a**). The chemical structure of self-healing polymer and hydrogen-bonding sites were deposited in **Figure 17b**. Compared with the conventional silicon electrode, the self-healing electrode possessed much longer cycling life even at a high current density of 2 A g^{-1} . Besides, the areal capacity of the self-healing electrode is $\sim 1.5-2.1 \text{ mA h cm}^{-2}$, close to the commercial requirement of 3 mA h cm^{-2} . Later, the interactions between self-healing polymer and Si particles were systematically studied by Chen and coworkers to improve the areal capacity and cycle stability.³¹⁷ Different from the SHP coated on the top of SiMP, a well-distributed 3D self-healing polymer coated on the SiMP electrode was designed (**Figure 17c**). Thus, a robust interaction between SiMP and the SHP was built throughout the electrode, endowing improvement of stability under high areal capacity. As a result, the as-prepared 3D SiMP coated with self-healing polymer electrodes demonstrated more than 140 cycles at high areal capacity ($3-4 \text{ mA h cm}^{-2}$). However, the moderate rate capability is induced by relatively slow charge transfer in the thick electrode. To further improve the rate performance, recently, a porous self-healing graphitic carbon/Si foam electrode was achieved and brought about a higher capacity.³¹⁸ An ionically

conductive self-healing polymer was used as the coating material for ameliorating the electrochemical performance of Si microparticles. In particular, polyethylene glycol (PEG) groups were incorporated into the SHP, combining the characteristics of self-healing and high ion conductivity. In detail, dynamic hydrogen bonding enables self-healing ability and promotes good adhesion by interaction with hydroxyl groups on the surface of Si microparticles (**Figure 17d**). The polyether units of various molecular weights and mass fractions of PEG were also investigated to facilitate Li-ion transfer in the matrix. As a result, although SHP-PEG2000 (100) exhibited a high ion conductivity ($6.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$), SHP-PEG750 (40) exhibited a better rate capacity at various current densities, benefiting from the stronger adhesion with Si particles and lower charge transfer resistance. The concept of self-healing binder, embedding both cycling stability and fast charging, should be equally effective for other high-capacity materials which suffer from huge volume change after cycling.

6. Conclusions and Perspectives

With the increasing development of electric vehicles and other power-intensive devices, restricted energy density and prolonged charging time are still common concerns for rechargeable batteries. Capacity and energy efficiency fading induced by excessive overpotential under high current density is the main factor holding back effective fast charging. Thus, mitigating capacity attenuation at high rates is one of the fundamental challenges facing the development of next-generation high-performance electrochemical batteries. Fast charging is multiple scales (time and length) and systematized problems, such as the electronic structure and morphology of the electrode materials, operational conditions, and battery packs. To push both fundamental research and practical applications of fast charging rechargeable batteries, in this review article, the new emerging microscale electrode materials and their considerations are summarized. Instead of only taking consideration of improving the ionic and electrical conductivity of electrode materials by a simple reduction in size, rational electrode material designs are proposed to satisfy the double standards of high volumetric packing density and high-power applications. To conclude, a comprehensive analysis

and discussion of micro-nano hybrid structure electrode materials, micro-sized gradient structure electrode materials, micron-sized electrode materials with appropriate crystal structures, and 3D microscale hybrid electrode materials are given in this review, which is a powerful measure to improve fast charging performance without sacrificing energy density as well as structural stability. As summarized in **Table 1**, just as every coin has two sides, there are also advantages and potential limitations for each design solution of micro-scale electrode materials.

1) Nonetheless, new microscale electrode materials involving rational architecture designs and advanced crystal structures can offer a promising direction of academic and application significance. However, so far there is almost no ideal strategy that can satisfy the requirements of industrial fast charging metrics. The gap between early electrode materials development and industrial applications challenges the practical use of the above-mentioned microscale electrode materials. More considerations and further efforts should be taken to bridge the gap in the following aspects.

2) Particle size distribution of electrode materials remains a critical factor for the volumetric packing density of batteries. A battery with optimum power production and energy storage will require control of the particle size distribution of electrode materials. When the particle size distribution is broad, the smaller particles can be filled in the gap of large particles, which is a benefit for increasing the tap density and volumetric packing density. Various mathematical models and experimental measurements should be investigated to shed more fresh light on the effect of geometry variations on battery chemistry and fast charging performance.

3) 3D microstructure characteristics have a great influence on the electrochemical and mechanical properties of batteries. Accurate capture of morphological details combined with machine learning facilitates the establishment of microstructure-resolved modeling and design methods for 3D microstructure of fast charging batteries. Recently, X-ray and electron using (laboratory and synchrotron sources) imaging techniques provide spatial and temporal quantifications of electrode morphologies, lithium transport phenomena and mechanical degradation mechanisms. Meanwhile,

machine learning translates collected data into specific design guidelines, establishes the relationship of microstructure–property for forwarding prediction and inverse design for fast charging batteries.

4) Rather than focusing on geometry variations and crystal structures of electrode materials, although rarely mentioned in this review, dynamics of ion and electron transport at the electrode/electrolyte interface, namely SEI and cathode electrolyte interphase (CEI), are also greatly important for fast charging performance.^{9, 319, 320} Therefore, the dynamic evolution of the interface characteristics deserves more investigation. Solid-state batteries without liquid organic electrolytes may provide an effective solution to this problem. Further work is required to get a more comprehensive understanding of various interface characteristics in all-solid-state batteries.

5) It is acknowledged as critical of thermal management associated with the fast charging process, which should control the temperature to maintain a thermal runaway offline. Besides, the temperature inhomogeneity induced by the current densities difference potentially leads to a lower voltage platform and localized failure. Furthermore, the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficient between active materials and other components may cause electrical contact failure. Further research is therefore needed to clarify the relationship between temperatures and various parameters of electrode materials, helping build up an effective thermal management system to monitor and identify the risks of thermal runaway.

6) Fast charging in cold or even freeze temperatures takes the risk of Li plating and cell failure. Few electrode designs or optimized charging strategies focus on addressing the issues in low-temperature fast charging. We thus call for the attention of researchers to speed up the development of fast charging in colder climates.

7) By combining the development of electronic/crystal structure and electrochemical theory with intelligent data mining, high-throughput computational materials design is a promising way to discover and evaluate the potential applications of candidate materials in fast charging batteries.³²¹

High throughput means both shortening the research and development time, lowering costs, and enhancing the success of the experiment, which can bridge the gap between laboratory and industrial applications.

8) Ultimately, given that fast charging batteries is a complicated system, evaluation standards of relevant testing parameters and key performance indicators should be put forward.^{322, 323} Such as voltage range, the quantity of electrolyte, mass loading, N/P ratio (ratio of negative electrode capacity to positive electrode capacity), energy density, battery-pack assembling process, and other sensitive parameters for testing performances occur in the gap between new electrode materials and industrial applications. Thus, understanding and standardizing the above parameters are conducive to getting valuable and reliable data. Application-oriented research should be evaluated standardized in the early stage, to accelerate the discovery of new materials and their practical application in battery systems.

9) As discussed in this review, the new emerging microscale electrode materials not only are promising for achieving high power and energy density Li-ion batteries but also can overcome the inherent limitations of nanomaterials, such as low tap density and side reactions. Understanding the mechanism of charge transport both on the active materials level and electrode level has always been a constant driving force for the improvement and discovery of electrode materials. Meanwhile, beyond Li batteries, other alkali ions (Na^+ , K^+) batteries and multivalent ion batteries (Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , etc.) share a similar charge transfer mechanism from both materials level and electrode level. It is considered that the microscale materials and electrode design would meet the requirement of practical utilization in fast charging energy storage devices

Table 1. Summary of various approaches for the micro-scale fast charging electrode materials

Strategies	Catalogue & Description	Resolution	Advantages	Potential limitations	References
Crystal structure design	Convincing strategy and high scalability	Particle-level (3~10 μm)	Improving intrinsic conductivity, high manufacturing efficiency	Limited voltage window	152
Nanolayer coating	electron-conducting layer	Particle-level (10 μm)	High tap density, medium performance	Inhomogeneous coating, no improving intrinsic conductivity	164
	ion-conducting layer	Particle-level (22 μm)			165
Microscale secondary materials	Nanoparticles included	Particle-level (~5 μm)	Medium tap density, medium performance, low interparticle resistance	No improving intrinsic conductivity, sacrificing volumetric packing density	171
	Micropores: store ions				
Microscale porous materials	Mesopores: fast ions transport channels	Particle-level (~6 μm)	Fast ions transport, high power density	High active surface area inducing low initial CE, sacrificing volumetric packing density	324
	Macropores: buffer volume change				
Surface gradient structure	Modified conventional core-shell structure	Particle-level (11.5, 18.6, 29.2 μm)	High structural stability, high tap density, high performance	More fabrication steps and high cost	193
FCG synergistic structure	Modified surface gradient structure and beyond	Particle-level (~5 μm)	Avoiding structure mismatch, medium tap density	Low fabrication efficiency, high cost	205

Metal-based 3D electrode materials	Self-standing electrode without other passive components	Electrode-level	3D interconnected network for efficient charge transfer, stable in tough environments	High density and sacrificing energy density	220
Carbon-based 3D electrode materials	Realize the full potential of electrode materials, regardless of the type of active material	Electrode-level	3D interconnected network for efficient charge transfer, high areal capacity, high-energy and high-power density	Potential failure of contact between active materials and framework, porous architecture sacrificing volumetric packing density	223
Magnetic alignment materials	Low tortuosity electrode configuration, self-standing electrode materials	Electrode-level (200 μm thick)	High areal capacity, practical application, medium performance	Sacrificing magnetic additives and volumetric packing density, impurities and residual may affect electrochemical performance	248, 249
Directional freeze-casting	Low tortuosity electrode configuration, self-standing electrode materials	Electrode-level (125 μm thick)	Without introducing impurities, high power density, high mass loading, high scalability	Porous sacrificing volumetric packing density, high active surface area	262, 263
Biomass-derived low-tortuosity host	Low tortuosity electrode configuration, self-standing electrode without other passive components	Electrode-level (800 μm thick)	Robust mechanical properties, superior charge transfer performance, high energy, and high power density, sustainable and biodegradable	Potential failure of contact between active materials and host, porous architectures sacrificing volumetric packing density	279, 281
LMA electrode materials	Self-healing features	Electrode-level	Dendrite-free even at high rates, high power density	Cathode host dependence, rigorous package procedure, potential safety issues, poor scalability	307, 309
Self-healing polymers assisted	Healing features in bulk electrode materials	Particle-level (3~8 μm)	Medium power density, high scalability, mechanical flexibility	Limited self-healing time (a few minutes to hours), low fabrication efficiency	316, 318

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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